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Combinator-Based Fixpoint Algorithms for Big-Step Abstract Interpreters (Journal Extension)

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Abstract

Big-step abstract interpreters are an approach to build static analyzers based on big-step interpretation. While big-step interpretation provides a number of benefits for the definition of an analysis, it also requires particularly complicated fixpoint algorithms because the analysis definition is a recursive function whose termination is uncertain. This is in contrast to other analysis approaches, such as small-step reduction, abstract machines, or graph reachability, where the analysis essentially forms a finite transition system between widened analysis states.

We show how to systematically develop sophisticated fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract interpreters and how to ensure their soundness. Our approach is based on small and reusable fixpoint combinators that can be composed to yield fixpoint algorithms. For example, these combinators describe the order in which the program is analyzed, how deep recursive functions are unfolded and loops unrolled, or they record auxiliary data such as a (context-sensitive) call graph. Importantly, each combinator can be developed separately, reused across analyses, and can be verified sound independently. Consequently, analysis developers can freely compose combinators to obtain sound fixpoint algorithms that work best for their use case. We provide a formal metatheory that guarantees a fixpoint algorithm is sound if its composed from sound combinators only. We experimentally validate our combinator-based approach by describing sophisticated fixpoint algorithms for analyses of Stratego, Scheme, WebAssembly, and Datalog.

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1 Introduction

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Abstract interpretation [7] is a methodology for defining sound static analyses. While in the past, many static analyses have been described as abstract interpreters in small-step style [10, 14, 29, 30, 39, 42], more recently big-step abstract interpreters have been investigated more thoroughly [3, 9, 18, 22, 50]. Such big-step abstract interpreters can be simply described as recursive functions in any meta-language; we use Haskell as a meta-language throughout this paper.

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Big-step abstract interpreters (sometimes called definitional abstract interpreters) look like the corresponding concrete interpreter, except they compute with abstract data. For example, consider the big-step abstract interpreter in [Listing 1](#) that approximates values

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52  $\widehat{\text{eval}} :: \text{Funs} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Env}} \rightarrow \text{Expr} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } \widehat{\text{Val}}$ 
53  $\widehat{\text{eval}} \text{ funName env expr} = \text{case expr of}$ 
54   Var x  $\rightarrow$  lookup x env
55   Num n  $\rightarrow$  return (n,n)
56   Add e1 e2  $\rightarrow$  do
57     (i1,i2)  $\leftarrow$   $\widehat{\text{eval}}$  funName env e1
58     (j1,j2)  $\leftarrow$   $\widehat{\text{eval}}$  funName env e2
59     return (i1+j1,i2+j2)
60   Call funName args  $\rightarrow$  do
61     let (params, body) = lookup funName funs
62         vs  $\leftarrow$  mapM args ( $\widehat{\text{eval}}$  funName env)
63          $\widehat{\text{eval}}$  funName (Map.fromList (zip params vs)) body
64
65   Expr = Var String
66         | Num Int
67         | Add Expr Expr
68         | Call String [Expr]
69         | ...
70
71   Funs = Map [String] ([String], Expr)
72    $\widehat{\text{Env}}$  = Map String  $\widehat{\text{Val}}$ 
73    $\widehat{\text{Val}}$  = Interval

```

Listing 1. A big-step abstract interpreter for a language with first-order functions. The abstract interpreter is sound but fails to terminate for diverging recursive functions.

using intervals. Big-step abstract interpreters like this are easy to understand [9] and reason about [22], while they seamlessly combine data-flow and control-flow information. However, our abstract interpreter does not terminate on all inputs, since it calls itself unconditionally in the last line of Listing 1. While non-termination is expected language behavior for concrete interpreters, it is undesirable for abstract interpreters. But how can we ensure our big-step abstract interpreter terminates?

In this work, we study fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract interpreters (*big-step fixpoint algorithms* for short) and how to describe and reason about them modularly. Like most fixpoint algorithms, big-step fixpoint algorithms must apply the abstract interpreter repeatedly until the analysis result is stable. However, the recursive definition of big-step abstract interpreters makes it difficult to ensure termination. In particular, it is insufficient to limit the number of call sites in the object language, because abstract interpreters still end up in an infinite recursive loop when calls recur. Schmidt [38] was the first to propose a fixpoint algorithm for big-step abstract interpreters. We reformulate his work and combine it with the chaotic iteration strategy of Bourdoncle [4] to derive a novel big-step fixpoint algorithm: a fixpoint algorithm based on chaotic iteration over strongly-connected subgraphs of the dynamically discovered graph-shaped trace of an abstract interpreter.

Our initial big-step fixpoint algorithm is sound and ensures termination, although its implementation and soundness proof are complex and monolithic. We argue that fixpoint algorithms should be described and proven sound modularly because practical analyses require specialized and fine-tuned fixpoint algorithms:

Specialized fixpoint algorithms. Different analyses and languages often require specialized fixpoint algorithms. For example, the Soot framework [25] describes 7 different fixpoint algorithms for different types of analyses: Two algorithms¹ for distributive analysis

¹<https://github.com/Sable/heros/blob/develop/src/heros/solver/IFDSSolver.java> and `IDESolver.java`

problems [35, 37], two algorithms² for bidirectional analyses problems such as taint analysis [26], two algorithms³ for flow-sensitive analysis problems [45], and one algorithm⁴ for context, flow and field-sensitive analysis problems [44].

However, it takes effort to develop and maintain many different fixpoint algorithms and their soundness proofs. Therefore many proofs become outdated over time and they become ineffective at guaranteeing soundness of the analysis.

Fine-tuning existing fixpoint algorithms. Fixpoint algorithms require continuous fine-tuning to yield satisfactory performance and precision. In particular, no fixpoint algorithm works best in all cases and configurability is key.

Unfortunately, fine-tuning a single monolithic fixpoint algorithm has two problems. First, tuning it for one analysis may lead to regressions for other analyses that use the same algorithm. Second, every change to the fixpoint algorithm can introduce a soundness bug, yet reestablishing the soundness proof for every single change is infeasible in practice. These two problems cause framework developers either to avoid fine-tuning their fixpoint algorithms or to avoid proving them sound rigorously.

To support such scenarios, we propose a novel approach for the implementation of big-step fixpoint algorithms based on reusable and separately verifiable *fixpoint combinators*. Note that we mean *combinators* in the sense of parser combinators, where complex functions can be constructed by composing simpler functions.⁵ For example, fixpoint combinators describe the order in which the program statements are analyzed, how deep recursive functions are unfolded or loops are unrolled, or they record auxiliary data such as a control-flow graph. A complete fixpoint algorithm can then be composed by choosing appropriate fixpoint combinators (each starting with φ):

```

129  $\varphi_{\text{filter}}$  isFunBody ( $\varphi_{\text{unfold}}$  3  $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$   $\circ$   $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ )
130
131 -- Types of the used combinators
132 Combinator a b = {- defined in section 3 -} Call = (Funs,  $\widehat{\text{Env}}$ , Expr) Result =  $\widehat{\text{Val}}$ 
133  $\varphi_{\text{filter}}$  isFunBody :: Combinator Call Result  $\rightarrow$  Combinator Call Result
134  $\varphi_{\text{unfold}}$  3 :: Combinator Call Result  $\rightarrow$  Combinator Call Result
135  $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$  :: Combinator Call Result
136  $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$  :: Combinator Call Result
137 ( $\circ$ ) :: Combinator Call Result  $\rightarrow$  Combinator Call Result  $\rightarrow$  Combinator Call Result
138

```

This fixpoint algorithm applies only to function bodies (φ_{filter} isFunBody) and unfolds the first 3 recursive function calls (φ_{unfold} 3) before it applies a widening operator on the stack ($\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$). In case of nested recursive function calls, the fixpoint algorithm stabilizes the analysis result of the innermost calls first ($\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$).

This modular description allows analysis developers to specialize and fine-tune fixpoint algorithms by reconfiguring individual combinators or adding specialized ones. For example,

²<https://github.com/Sable/heros/blob/develop/src/heros/solver/BiDiIFDSSolver.java> and [BiDiIDESolver.java](https://github.com/Sable/heros/blob/develop/src/heros/solver/BiDiIDESolver.java)

³<https://github.com/Sable/heros/blob/develop/src/heros/fieldsens/FieldSensitiveIFDSSolver.java> and

[FieldSensitiveBiDiIFDSSolver.java](https://github.com/Sable/heros/blob/develop/src/heros/fieldsens/FieldSensitiveBiDiIFDSSolver.java)

⁴<https://github.com/CodeShield-Security/SPDS/blob/master/WPDS/src/main/java/wpds/impl/>

[WeightedPAutomaton.java](https://github.com/CodeShield-Security/SPDS/blob/master/WPDS/src/main/java/wpds/impl/WeightedPAutomaton.java)

⁵Technically, we mean *non-standard* fixpoint combinators φ that do not necessarily satisfy the standard fixpoint property $\varphi(f) = f(\varphi(f))$, but rather $\varphi(f) \sqsupseteq f(\varphi(f))$, which is sufficient for soundness.

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we can extend the fixpoint algorithm from above to record the call graph (φ_{CFG}) and to handle while-loops:

```
 $\varphi_{filter} \text{ isFunBody } (\varphi_{CFG} \circ \varphi_{unfold}^3 \varphi_{stackWiden} \circ \varphi_{innermost}) \circ$   
 $\varphi_{filter} \text{ isWhileLoop } (\varphi_{unroll} 10 \varphi_{stackWiden} \circ \varphi_{outermost})$ 
```

This fixpoint algorithm seamlessly interleaves the intra-procedural analysis of loops with the inter-procedural analysis of recursive function calls. Both of these aspects can be individually changed and fine-tuned by adding, replacing, and reordering fixpoint combinators. And of course we can use standard function abstraction to make parts of the fixpoint algorithm reusable.

We also modularize the soundness proofs of big-step fixpoint algorithms by developing a formal theory for fixpoint combinators. The modularization simplifies the effort and complexity of these soundness proofs and makes them composable. In particular, we prove that a modular fixpoint algorithm is sound if all of its combinators are sound. This not only simplifies the initial soundness proof for a fixpoint algorithm but also makes it easier to reestablish soundness after a change.

We demonstrate that our approach is feasible and useful by implementing it in Haskell as part of the *Sturdy* framework [18, 22]. We developed 12 fixpoint combinators and composed them to obtain fixpoint algorithms for 3 analyses of 4 different languages: WebAssembly, Stratego, Scheme and Datalog. We use these case studies to assess the language and analysis-independence, the precision, and the performance of the fixpoint algorithms. We find that the initial fixpoint algorithms perform poorly, but they can be easily specialized to the analysis without changing the implementation of any of the fixpoint combinators. We conclude that configurable fixpoint algorithms are necessary to allow analysis developers to fine-tune their analyses.

In this extended journal version of the original ICFP paper [20], we present a newly designed and improved implementation of the fixpoint combinators in Scala. While the general idea of the fixpoint combinators remains the same, the Scala implementation of the combinators is simpler and more optimized compared to the Haskell combinators. Specifically, the Scala combinators reuse cached analysis results more often, instead of redundantly reanalyzing parts of the program. This improves the running time of the combinators by orders of magnitude. We evaluate the performance of the optimized Scala combinators on analyses for WebAssembly [5] and Datalog. For WebAssembly the optimizations improve performance between 0.9–50 and for Datalog between 4–52.

As part of the original ICFP paper [20], we make the following contributions:

- We combine prior work on big-step fixpoint algorithms [38] and chaotic iteration [4] to develop a novel big-step fixpoint algorithm (Section 2).
- We propose an approach to modularize the description of big-step fixpoint algorithms through sound and reusable fixpoint combinators (Section 3).
- We present a library of reusable fixpoint combinators that serve as building blocks for developing fixpoint algorithms (Section 4).
- We develop a formal theory for these combinators that allows us to prove their soundness separately and once and for all (Section 5).
- We demonstrate that our approach is feasible and useful by implementing it in Haskell as part of the *Sturdy* framework (Section 6).

As part of the journal extension, we make the following contributions:

- We describe a newly designed simpler implementation of the fixpoint combinators in Scala (Section 7).
- We optimize the combinators to avoid redundant reanalysis and improve their performance (Section 8).
- We evaluate the performance of the combinators on WebAssembly and Datalog analyses (Section 8.3).

2 Designing Big-Step Fixpoint Algorithms

In this section, we first describe conditions that guarantee the termination of big-step fixpoint algorithms. In the second half, we develop a big-step fixpoint algorithm that satisfies these conditions.

2.1 Enforcing Termination of Big-Step Fixpoint Algorithms

Schmidt [38] introduced big-step abstract interpretation and showed how to compute its fixpoint. We reformulate his findings as three conditions that guarantee the termination of big-step fixpoint algorithms. Consider the analysis of the factorial function implemented in a language with first-order functions. The following diagram shows a big-step reduction trace of an abstract interpreter with unbounded recursion, where $\rho \vdash e \Downarrow v$ evaluates an expression e under environment ρ to an abstract value v . Such a trace looks similar to the trace of a concrete big-step interpreter, except that the values are intervals.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \vdots \\
 \hline
 n \mapsto [0, \infty] \vdash \text{if}(n == 0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ? \\
 \hline
 \frac{n \mapsto [1, \infty] \vdash \text{fact}(n - 1) \Downarrow ?}{n \mapsto [1, \infty] \vdash \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ?} \\
 \hline
 \frac{n \mapsto [0, 0] \vdash 1 \Downarrow [1, 1] \quad \frac{n \mapsto [1, \infty] \vdash \text{fact}(n - 1) \Downarrow ?}{n \mapsto [1, \infty] \vdash \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ?}}{n \mapsto [0, \infty] \vdash \text{if}(n == 0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ?} \\
 \hline
 n \mapsto [0, \infty] \vdash \text{fact}(n) \Downarrow ? \\
 \hline
 \text{fact}(n) = \text{if}(n == 0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n - 1) * n
 \end{array}$$

The analysis starts at the call $\text{fact}(n)$, where n is bound to the interval $[0, \infty]$ in the environment. Because the interval $[0, \infty]$ contains 0 and other numbers, the abstract interpreter has to evaluate both branches of the conditional $\text{if}(n == 0)$ and join the results. Whereas the analysis of the first branch terminates after only one step, the second branch diverges while recurrently calling the factorial function with the same environment over and over again (see **highlighted** calls). We write the question mark symbol to represent that the abstract interpreter diverged and did not produce a result. This leads us to the first condition:

Condition 1 *A big-step fixpoint algorithm has to detect recurrent recursive calls and cut off recursion to avoid non-termination.*

Detecting recurrent calls allows the fixpoint algorithm to iterate that part of the computation that spans the initial call and the recurrent call. One way of detecting recurrent recursive calls is to remember the calls of the abstract interpreter on each branch of the derivation tree. Each call consists of the inputs of the abstract interpreter, e.g., an expression and an environment. By remembering the calls, we can easily detect a diverging call, if the exact same call occurred earlier, further down the derivation branch.

However, this way of detecting recurrent recursive calls is insufficient. For example, consider the analysis of the factorial function for negative arguments. Clearly, the factorial function does not terminate for negative arguments, and we expect the abstract interpreter to return an analysis result that represents non-termination. Instead, the abstract interpreter itself diverges:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \vdots \\
 n \mapsto [-\infty, -2] \vdash \text{if}(n == 0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ? \\
 \vdots \\
 \hline
 n \mapsto [-\infty, -1] \vdash \text{if}(n == 0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n - 1) * n \Downarrow ? \\
 \hline
 n \mapsto [-\infty, -1] \vdash \text{fact}(n) \Downarrow ? \\
 \\
 \text{fact}(n) = \text{if}(n==0) \ 1 \ \text{else} \ \text{fact}(n-1) * n
 \end{array}$$

The abstract interpreter analyzes the factorial function with smaller and smaller intervals, because factorial decrements its argument on every recursive call. Even though the intervals become smaller, the chain of recursive calls is still infinite. Therefore, the fixpoint algorithm never encounters a recurrent recursive call. This means that a fixpoint algorithm that satisfies the first condition still may not terminate. This leads us to the second condition:

Condition 2 *A big-step fixpoint algorithm has to ensure that all possibly infinite call chains have a recurrent call.*

In other words, all call chains are either finite or repeat themselves after finitely many calls. This ensures that a fixpoint algorithm can find a recurrent call even in infinite call chains.

While the first and second condition concern the inputs of the abstract interpreter, the third condition concerns its outputs. To illustrate this condition, consider an interval analysis of the multiplication function on Peano numbers, where we initially bind m to $[1, \infty]$ and n to $[1, 1]$.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 m \mapsto [1, \infty], n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash \text{if}(m == 1) \ n \ \text{else} \ \text{mult}(m - 1, n) + n \Downarrow X \\
 \hline
 m \mapsto [2, \infty], n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash \text{mult}(m - 1, n) \Downarrow X \\
 \hline
 n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash n \Downarrow [1, 1] \quad m \mapsto [2, \infty], n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash \text{mult}(m - 1, n) + n \Downarrow X + [1, 1] \\
 \hline
 m \mapsto [1, \infty], n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash \text{if}(m == 1) \ n \ \text{else} \ \text{mult}(m - 1, n) + n \Downarrow [1, 1] \sqcup (X + [1, 1]) \\
 \hline
 m \mapsto [1, \infty], n \mapsto [1, 1] \vdash \text{mult}(m, n) \Downarrow ? \\
 \\
 \text{mult}(m, n) = \text{if}(m==1) \ n \ \text{else} \ \text{mult}(m-1, n) + n
 \end{array}$$

The right-hand side branch of the derivation tree contains a recurrent call of `mult`. In this example, we represent the result of the recurrent call with a symbolic variable X . By tracing back the result to the initial call of `mult`, we obtain the recursive equation $X = [1, 1] \sqcup (X + [1, 1])$. An established technique for solving such an equation is to start with the empty interval \perp and then to proceed iteratively until reaching a fixpoint [8]. However, starting with \perp , this technique does not reach a fixpoint in a finite number of steps for our example:

$$X_0 = \perp \quad X_1 = [1, 1] \sqcup (X_0 + [1, 1]) = [1, 1] \quad X_2 = [1, 1] \sqcup (X_1 + [1, 1]) = [1, 2] \quad \dots$$

This example shows that even if a big-step fixpoint algorithm ensures and detects recurrent calls, it still might iterate on the analysis result indefinitely. This leads us to the third condition:

Condition 3 *A big-step fixpoint algorithm may only iterate the results a finite number of times.*

Our three conditions guarantee termination:

THEOREM 2.1 (TERMINATION). *If a big-step fixpoint algorithm satisfies the three termination conditions and all evaluation rules have a finite branching factor, then the big-step fixpoint algorithm terminates.*

PROOF. *Condition 1* and *2* ensure that each infinite call chain is eventually cut off at a recurrent call and hence is finite. *Condition 3* ensures that the fixpoint algorithm iterates on the analysis result for each node of the tree finitely many times. Finite call chains, finite iteration, and the finite branching factor of the rules guarantee that the big-step derivation tree is finite. Therefore, the fixpoint algorithm terminates. \square

To summarize, a big-step fixpoint algorithm terminates if it satisfies the termination conditions. In the following subsection, we describe a big-step fixpoint algorithm that satisfies the termination conditions.

2.2 A Big-Step Fixpoint Algorithm that iterates on Strongly-Connected Subgraphs

In this section, we describe a novel fixpoint algorithm for big-step abstract interpreters that iterates on the strongly-connected subgraph of the graph-shaped trace of the abstract interpreter. The fixpoint algorithm targets the simple functional language from [Section 2.1](#), but we generalize it in [Section 3](#) by making it language-independent and modular.

The fixpoint algorithm iterates on the strongly-connected subgraphs (SCGs) of the graph-shaped trace of the abstract interpreter [4]. An SCG is a set of calls from which it is possible to reach all other calls in the same set. SCGs in the abstract interpreter trace occur if the analyzed program has cyclic dependencies, such as loops or recursive functions. For example, consider the graph-shaped trace to the right for the analysis of the Fibonacci function starting at call $\text{fib}[1, \infty]$. We write $\text{fib}[i, j]$ as a shorthand for a call $[n \mapsto [i, j]] \vdash \text{fib}(n)$. The graph has an *outer* SCG and an *inner* SCG indicated by the differently shaded areas. The solid arrows indicate calls and returns in the order in which they are executed by the abstract interpreter. The dotted arrows indicate recurrent calls. A call is recurrent when that same call is already on the call stack. In our example, we have three recurrent calls and the dotted arrow indicates the outermost dominator. We explain later in [Figure 1](#) how this trace is computed in more detail.

To compute a fixpoint, the algorithm has to iterate on all calls in the body of an SCG. The order in which the fixpoint algorithm iterates over the calls does not matter for soundness [4], but affects performance and precision of the analysis. In this section we present an algorithm that prioritizes calls in the *innermost* SCGs, before iterating on the outer SCGs. The trace of the abstract interpreter only becomes known while the analysis is running. Hence, the fixpoint algorithm cannot compute SCGs a priori and instead it must discover SCGs on the fly while the analysis is running. To detect SCGs, our algorithm tracks recurrent calls, because some recurrent calls are the entry calls of SCGs. For example, in the trace of the Fibonacci function

```
fib(n) = if(n==0) 0
        else if(n==1) 1
        else fib(n-1) + fib(n-2)
```


above the recurrent call $\text{fib}[0, \infty]$ points to the entry call of the inner SCG (rightmost dotted arrow), whereas the recurrent calls of $\text{fib}[1, \infty]$ point to the entry call of the outer SCG. To detect the *innermost* SCGs, the algorithm looks for the first recurrent call that it encounters upon returning.

Listing 2 shows the adapted abstract interpreter $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ and the main fixpoint algorithm $\widehat{\text{fix}}_{\text{monolithic}}$. Instead of calling itself recursively like in Listing 1, the abstract interpreter $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ calls $\widehat{\text{fix}}_{\text{monolithic}}$ to evaluate subexpressions, and $\widehat{\text{fix}}_{\text{monolithic}}$ calls $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ mutually recursive. This allows us to encapsulate the fixpoint logic in $\widehat{\text{fix}}_{\text{monolithic}}$, whereas $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ captures the rest of the abstract language semantics, which we do not show for brevity. Our fixpoint algorithm uses three data structures: A map $\widehat{\text{Stack}}$ to detect recurrent calls, storing for each expression Expr the abstract environment $\widehat{\text{Env}}$ under which the expression is evaluated. A map $\widehat{\text{Cache}}$ to iterate on analysis results, storing for each abstract $\widehat{\text{Call}}$ the abstract value $\widehat{\text{Val}}$ to which the call evaluated. A set $\widehat{\text{SCG}}$ to detect which calls need to be iterated, containing recurrent recursive calls.

The algorithm first checks in line 14, if the expression is the top-level expression in a function body and hence a potentially diverging call. If the expression is not the top-level expression in a function body (e.g., a numeric operator), no iteration is necessary to find a fixpoint and we can simply call $\widehat{\text{eval}}$. This not only saves analysis time, but also reduces the size of the stack and cache tremendously. If the expression is the top-level of a function body, the algorithm applies a widening operator [8] ∇_{Stack} to the stack and the call. This widening operator ensures that all infinite non-repeating stacks eventually have a recurrent call (*Condition 2*). We explain this operator in more detail below. The algorithm then checks if the cache contains a stable analysis result for the call and returns this result to avoid redundant reanalysis (line 15). Analysis results are stable if they do not grow anymore when reevaluated and if they solely depend on other stable analysis results. If the cache only contains an unstable or no analysis result, the algorithm checks if the call (funs , env , expr) is a recurrent call by searching for it on the stack. In case of a recurrent call, the algorithm satisfies *Condition 1* by either returning the unstable analysis result (line 16) or returning \perp (line 17). Furthermore, since the analysis result needs to be iterated on, the algorithm adds its call to the SCG set. If the call does not appear on the stack, the algorithm calls a recursive helper function iterate (line 18) that iterates the analysis result until it stabilizes.

Function iterate is responsible for iterating on calls in SCGs. In line 24, the algorithm calls the abstract interpreter $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ with the current input. The algorithm then iterates on the call, in case the call is a head of an SCG (line 25), or otherwise simply returns the result of $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ (line 33). In line 27, the algorithm uses a widening operator for values $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{val}}}$ to ensure that the analysis result does not grow indefinitely (*Condition 3*).⁶ If the widened value is strictly greater than the cached value, the algorithm keeps iterating (line 31). Otherwise, if the widened value did not grow anymore, the algorithm terminates the iteration, returns the widened value, and removes the call from the SCG since it does not require iteration anymore (line 32).

The widening operator ∇_{Stack} ensures that all infinite non-repeating stacks eventually have a recurrent call (*Condition 2*). If the expression appeared on the stack and the environment of the call is smaller than the environment on the stack (line 37), the stack widening operator

⁶In case of an analysis over lattices of finite height, the widening operator (∇) can be replaced by the least upper bound operator (\sqcup).

```

409 1  $\widehat{\text{Stack}} = \text{Map Expr } \widehat{\text{Env}} \quad \widehat{\text{Cache}} = \text{Map } \widehat{\text{Call}} (\widehat{\text{Stability}}, \widehat{\text{Val}}) \quad \widehat{\text{SCG}} = \text{Set } \widehat{\text{Call}}$ 
410 2  $\widehat{\text{Call}} = (\text{Funs}, \widehat{\text{Env}}, \text{Expr}) \quad \widehat{\text{Stability}} = \text{Stable} \mid \text{Unstable}$ 
411 3
412 4  $\widehat{\text{eval}} :: \widehat{\text{Call}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Stack}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Cache}} \rightarrow (\widehat{\text{Val}}, \widehat{\text{Cache}}, \widehat{\text{SCG}})$ 
413 5  $\widehat{\text{eval}} (\text{funs}, \text{env}, \text{expr}) \text{ stack } \text{cache}_1 = \text{case expr of}$ 
414 6   Add  $e_1 e_2 \rightarrow$ 
415 7     let  $((i_1, i_2), \text{cache}_2, \text{scg}_1) = \text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} (\text{funs}, \text{env}, e_1) \text{ stack } \text{cache}_1$ 
416 8          $((j_1, j_2), \text{cache}_3, \text{scg}_2) = \text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} (\text{funs}, \text{env}, e_2) \text{ stack } \text{cache}_2$ 
417 9     in  $((i_1 + j_1, i_2 + j_2), \text{cache}_3, \text{scg}_1 \cup \text{scg}_2)$ 
418 10   ...
419 11
420 12  $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} :: \widehat{\text{Call}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Stack}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Cache}} \rightarrow (\widehat{\text{Val}}, \widehat{\text{Cache}}, \widehat{\text{SCG}})$ 
421 13  $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} \text{ call } \text{stack } \text{cache}$ 
422 14   | not (isFunctionBody call) =  $\widehat{\text{eval}} \text{ call } \text{stack } \text{cache}$ 
423 15   |  $\text{call}_{\text{widened}} \in \text{cache} \wedge \text{val}_{\text{stability}} == \text{Stable}$  =  $(\text{val}_{\text{cached}}, \text{cache}, \emptyset)$ 
424 16   |  $\text{call}_{\text{widened}} \in \text{cache} \wedge \text{val}_{\text{stability}} == \text{Unstable}$  =  $(\text{val}_{\text{cached}}, \text{cache}, \{\text{call}_{\text{widened}}\})$ 
425 17   |  $\text{call}_{\text{widened}} \notin \text{cache} \wedge \text{call}_{\text{widened}} \in \text{stack}_{\text{widened}}$  =  $(\perp, \text{cache}, \{\text{call}_{\text{widened}}\})$ 
426 18   |  $\text{call}_{\text{widened}} \notin \text{cache} \wedge \text{call}_{\text{widened}} \notin \text{stack}_{\text{widened}}$  =  $\text{iterate } \text{call}_{\text{widened}} \text{ stack}_{\text{widened}} \text{ cache}$ 
427 19   where  $(\text{val}_{\text{stability}}, \text{val}_{\text{cached}}) = \text{cache}(\text{call}_{\text{widened}})$ 
428 20          $(\text{stack}_{\text{widened}}, \text{call}_{\text{widened}}) = \text{stack } \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} \text{ call}$ 
429 21
430 22  $\text{iterate} :: \widehat{\text{Call}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Stack}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Cache}} \rightarrow (\widehat{\text{Val}}, \widehat{\text{Cache}}, \widehat{\text{SCG}})$ 
431 23  $\text{iterate } \text{call } \text{stack } \text{cache}_1 =$ 
432 24   let  $(\text{val}_{\text{new}}, \text{cache}_2, \text{scg}) = \widehat{\text{eval}} \text{ call } \text{stack } \text{cache}_1$ 
433 25   if  $\text{call} \in \text{scg}$  then
434 26     let  $\text{val}_{\text{old}} = \text{if } \text{call} \in \text{cache}_2 \text{ then } \text{cache}_2(\text{call}) \text{ else } \perp$ 
435 27          $\text{val}_{\text{widened}} = \text{val}_{\text{old}} \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Val}}} \text{val}_{\text{new}}$ 
436 28          $\text{stability} = \text{if } \text{val}_{\text{widened}} \sqsubseteq \text{val}_{\text{old}} \wedge \text{size } \text{scg} == 1 \text{ then } \text{Stable} \text{ else } \text{Unstable}$ 
437 29          $\text{cache}_3 = \text{cache}_2[\text{call} \mapsto (\text{stability}, \text{val}_{\text{widened}})]$ 
438 30     if  $\text{val}_{\text{old}} \sqsubseteq \text{val}_{\text{widened}}$ 
439 31     then  $\text{iterate } \text{call } \text{stack } \text{cache}_3$ 
440 32     else  $(\text{val}_{\text{widened}}, \text{cache}_3, \text{scg} \setminus \{\text{call}\})$ 
441 33   else  $(\text{val}_{\text{new}}, \text{cache}_2, \text{scg})$ 
442 34
443 35  $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} :: \widehat{\text{Stack}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Call}} \rightarrow (\widehat{\text{Stack}}, \widehat{\text{Call}})$ 
444 36  $\text{stack } \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} (\text{funs}, \text{env}_1, \text{expr})$ 
445 37   |  $\text{expr} \in \text{dom } \text{stack} \wedge \text{env}_1 \sqsubseteq \text{env}_2 = (\text{stack}, (\text{funs}, \text{env}_2, \text{expr}))$ 
446 38   |  $\text{expr} \in \text{dom } \text{stack} \wedge \text{env}_1 \not\sqsubseteq \text{env}_2 = (\text{stack}[\text{expr} \mapsto \text{env}_{\text{widened}}], (\text{funs}, \text{env}_{\text{widened}}, \text{expr}))$ 
447 39   |  $\text{expr} \notin \text{dom } \text{stack} = (\text{stack}[\text{expr} \mapsto \text{env}_1], (\text{funs}, \text{env}_1, \text{expr}))$ 
448 40   where  $\text{env}_2 = \text{stack}(\text{expr})$ 
449 41          $\text{env}_{\text{widened}} = \text{env}_2 \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Env}}} \text{env}_1$ 
450 42
451 43  $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{Env}}} :: \widehat{\text{Env}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Env}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Env}}$ 
452 44  $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{Val}}} :: \widehat{\text{Val}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Val}} \rightarrow \widehat{\text{Val}}$ 

```

Listing 2. Big-step fixpoint algorithm iterating on the innermost strongly-connected subgraph. The code uses common mathematical notation for operations on maps and sets for readability. In particular, the notation $\text{cache}(\text{call})$ looks up the key call in the map cache and the notation $\text{cache}[\text{call} \mapsto \text{res}]$ updates the map entry call to res . Furthermore, $\{\text{call}\}$ refers to the singleton set with the element call .

Fig. 1. Example trace of the abstract interpreter analyzing the Fibonacci function. Arrow \hookrightarrow represents a call, arrow \downarrow a return, and arrow \Leftrightarrow an iteration. The highlighting indicates which results changed between consecutive iteration. The indentation level indicates the depth of the stack.

introduces a recurrent call by reusing the environment on the stack. If the environment on the stack is not an upper bound of the environment in the call (line 38), the stack widening operator applies a widening operator $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{ENV}}}$ to both environments. Operator $\nabla_{\widehat{\text{ENV}}}$ computes an upper bound of both environments and ensures that the environment under which an expression is evaluated cannot grow infinitely. Lastly, in case the expression did not occur on the stack (line 39), the operator adds the call to the stack without changing it.

We illustrate how this algorithm works with an example of the analysis of the Fibonacci function. Figure 1 shows a trace of the abstract interpreter starting at $\text{fib}[1, \infty]$. To make the internals of the fixpoint algorithm visible, we write $\hookrightarrow \langle e, \rho, \sigma \rangle$ for a call e with stack ρ and cache σ . Furthermore, we write $\downarrow \langle v, \sigma, \theta \rangle$ for a return from a call with result value v , output cache σ , and SCG θ . Sometimes we show intermediate steps in the abstract interpretation, where we allow v to be an expression that evaluates to an interval. The highlighting indicates which analysis results changed between consecutive iterations.

The algorithm alternately iterates the innermost and the outermost SCG shown in the bottom right of Figure 1. In the beginning the algorithm explores the recursive calls of the fibonacci function until it hits the recurrent calls (lines 2, 4, and 5 in Figure 1). In these cases the algorithm returns \perp to avoid non-termination and adds the call to the SCG set (line 17

in Listing 2). Later the algorithm returns to the call of $\text{fib}[0,\infty]$ (line 6 in Figure 1) and iterates because the call is in SCG set θ_2 and the result interval has grown from \perp to $[0,1]$ (lines 25 and 30 in Listing 2). The following iteration propagates the new analysis result $\text{fib}[0,\infty] \mapsto [0,1]$ throughout the inner SCG. After returning to call $\text{fib}[0,\infty]$ (line 10 in Figure 1), the result did not grow and the algorithm returns to the surrounding call $\text{fib}[1,\infty]$, removing call $\text{fib}[0,\infty]$ from the SCG set (line 32 in Listing 2). Since the result for $\text{fib}[1,\infty]$ has grown from \perp to $[1,1]$, the algorithm iterates again and propagates the new analysis result $\text{fib}[1,\infty] \mapsto [1,1]$ throughout the outer SCG. After returning to call $\text{fib}[0,\infty]$ (line 17 in Figure 1), the result has grown from $[0,1]$ to $[0,2]$ and hence the algorithm widens the result to $[0,1] \nabla_{\widehat{\text{val}}} [0,2] = [0,\infty]$ (line 27 in Listing 2). Since the result is greater after widening, the algorithm iterates the call $\text{fib}[0,\infty]$ again until it does not grow anymore. Finally, after one more iteration of call $\text{fib}[1,\infty]$, the result $[1,\infty]$ does not grow anymore (line 25 in Figure 1) and the algorithm sets the cache entry to stable (line 28 in Listing 2).

In summary, we developed a big-step fixpoint algorithm that iterates on the strongly-connected subgraphs of the graph-shaped trace and satisfies the termination conditions. We prove soundness of this algorithm in Section 5.

3 Modular Description of Big-Step Fixpoint Algorithms

In the previous section, we discussed a big-step fixpoint algorithm that iterates on the strongly-connected subgraphs of the graph-shaped trace. Even though the initial fixpoint algorithm works and is sound, it is hard to specialize and fine-tune it. We can solve these problems by *modularizing* the description of big-step fixpoint algorithms, which we discuss in this section. We illustrate the modular description by refactoring the function $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ into smaller reusable fixpoint combinators. Additionally, this modularization will enable us to prove soundness of the fixpoint algorithm modularly, which we discuss in Section 5.

Language-Independence. The problem that makes function $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ language-dependent is that it refers to the abstract interpreter $\widehat{\text{eval}}$, environments, expressions, and values from the analyzed language directly. To make the algorithm language-independent, we first remove references to language-specific types. As first step, we replace the inputs $(\widehat{\text{Env}}, \widehat{\text{Expr}})$ and outputs $\widehat{\text{Val}}$ of the abstract interpreter with the type variables a and b .

$$\widehat{\text{Stack}} \ a = \text{Set } a \qquad \widehat{\text{Cache}} \ a \ b = \text{Map } a \ (\text{Stable}, b) \qquad \widehat{\text{SCG}} \ a = \text{Set } a$$

As second step, we remove the reference to $\widehat{\text{eval}}$ by turning it into an open-recursive style and passing its body as an argument to $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$. This allows us to implement $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ independently of the analyzed language.

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{eval}} &:: (\text{Funs}, \widehat{\text{Env}}, \widehat{\text{Expr}}) \Downarrow \widehat{\text{Val}} \\ \widehat{\text{eval}} &= \text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} \ (\lambda \widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \ ((\text{funs}, \text{env}, \text{expr}), \text{stack}, \text{cache}) \rightarrow \\ &\quad \text{case expr of } \dots \widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \ ((\text{funs}, \text{env}', \text{expr}'), \text{stack}, \text{cache}) \dots) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} :: (a \Downarrow b \rightarrow a \Downarrow b) \rightarrow a \Downarrow b$$

To this end, we introduced a type (\Downarrow) to represent the type of fixpoint computation:

$$a \Downarrow b = (a, \widehat{\text{Stack}} \ a, \widehat{\text{Cache}} \ a \ b) \rightarrow (b, \widehat{\text{Cache}} \ a \ b, \widehat{\text{SCG}} \ a)$$

We refrain from showing the new code of $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ until after the second refactoring.

Reusable Fixpoint Combinators. To make the fixpoint algorithm easier to specialize to a new analysis, we make two more changes. First, instead of implementing one single monolithic fixpoint algorithm, we split its functionality across multiple smaller fixpoint combinators $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n$. These combinators are then called by a function `fix` in a round-robin fashion, such that each combinator has the chance to affect the fixpoint computation:

```

562  $\widehat{\text{eval}} = \text{fix}_\varphi (\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \rightarrow \text{proc expr} \rightarrow \text{do}$ 
563
564 case expr of
565
566   Add  $e_1 e_2 \rightarrow \text{do}$ 
567
568      $(i_1, i_2) \leftarrow \widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \prec e_1$ 
569      $(j_1, j_2) \leftarrow \widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \prec e_2$ 
570     return  $\prec (i_1 + j_1, i_2 + j_2)$ 
571     ...
572
573  $\text{fix}_\varphi :: (a \Downarrow b \rightarrow a \Downarrow b) \rightarrow a \Downarrow b$ 
574  $\text{fix}_\varphi f = \varphi (f (\text{fix}_\varphi f))$ 
575
576  $\varphi :: a \Downarrow b \rightarrow a \Downarrow b$ 
577  $\varphi f (\text{call}, \text{stack}, \text{cache}) =$ 
578  $\varphi_1(\varphi_2(\dots \varphi_n(f) \dots)) (\text{call}, \text{stack}, \text{cache})$ 
579

```

In particular, $\text{fix}_\varphi (\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \dots)$ invokes combinator φ . Combinator φ then invokes combinator φ_1 , which then may invoke φ_2 , and so on, until eventually the last combinator φ_n calls $(\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \dots) (\text{fix}_\varphi (\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \dots))$ and the cycle repeats.

Even though this design of fixpoint combinators allows us to separate concerns, their type $a \Downarrow b$ is not fully extensible, as some combinators may need some extra data not present in the stack or the cache. Therefore, as second change, we generalize the type $a \Downarrow b$ to an arrow type $c \text{ a b}$ [15]. The arrow type reads as “some effectful computation c that takes values of type a as input and produces values of type b as output.” Arrows allow us to implement fixpoint combinators without having to refer to a specific type of fixpoint computation. They are particularly useful for implementing big-step fixpoint algorithms, because they cleanly separate the inputs of an effectful computation from the outputs. Moreover, they have proven useful for modularizing other parts of the abstract interpreter [18, 19, 22].

Refactoring the fixpoint algorithm. Based on these principles, we now refactor the fixpoint algorithm $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ into three reusable combinators $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$, φ_{filter} , and $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$.

The combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ is a stripped down version of the $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}}$ algorithm and only satisfies *Condition 1* and *3*.

```

595
596 1  $\varphi_{\text{innermost}} :: \dots \Rightarrow c \text{ a b} \rightarrow c \text{ a b}$ 
597 2  $\varphi_{\text{innermost}} f = \text{proc call} \rightarrow \text{do}$ 
598 3    $(\text{stable}, \text{result}_{\text{cached}}) \leftarrow$ 
599 4   Cache.lookup  $\prec$  call
600 5   if stable
601 6   then return  $\prec$   $\text{result}_{\text{cached}}$ 
602 7   else do
603 8      $\text{recurrentCall} \leftarrow \text{Stack.elem} \prec$  call
604 9     if recurrentCall then do
605 10      SCG.add  $\prec$  call
606 11      return  $\prec$   $\text{result}_{\text{cached}}$ 
607 12     else iterate f  $\prec$  call
608 13
609 14
610 15
611 16
612 17
613 18  $\text{iterate} :: \dots \Rightarrow c \text{ a b} \rightarrow c \text{ a b}$ 
614 19  $\text{iterate } f = \text{proc call} \rightarrow \text{do}$ 
615 20    $\text{result}_{\text{new}} \leftarrow \text{Stack.push } f \prec$  call
616 21    $\text{callInSCG} \leftarrow \text{SCG.elem} \prec$  call
617 22   if callInSCG then do
618 23      $(\text{grown}, \text{result}_{\text{widened}}) \leftarrow$ 
619 24     Cache.update  $\prec$   $(\text{call}, \text{result}_{\text{new}})$ 
620 25     if grown then iterate f  $\prec$  call
621 26     else do
622 27        $\text{sizeSCG} \leftarrow \text{SCG.size} \prec$  ()
623 28       if sizeSCG == 1
624 29       then Cache.setStable  $\prec$  call
625 30       else return  $\prec$  ()
626 31       SCG.remove  $\prec$  call
627 32       return  $\prec$   $\text{result}_{\text{widened}}$ 
628 33     else return  $\prec$   $\text{result}_{\text{new}}$ 

```

613 The combinator is parameterized by operations to access and modify the stack, cache, and
 614 SCG contained in the effectful arrow computation. Furthermore, the code uses the following
 615 arrow notation: The keyword `proc x` introduces a new arrow computation that binds its
 616 argument to the variable `x`. The syntax `y ← f < x` calls an arrow computation `f` with the
 617 argument `x` and binds the result to the variable `y`. Lastly, the keyword `return < x` returns
 618 `x` as result of the arrow computation, but does not exit the surrounding `proc` like regular
 619 returns.

620 The combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ first looks up the call in the cache. If the cached result is stable,
 621 the combinator simply returns the cached entry (line 6). Otherwise, the combinator looks up
 622 the call on the stack (line 8). In case of a recurrent call (line 9), the algorithm adds the call
 623 to the SCG and returns the cached entry. Otherwise, if the call did not appear on the stack
 624 (line 12), the algorithm calls the recursive helper function `iterate` that updates the analysis
 625 result until it does not grow anymore. The function `iterate` first calls the computation `f`
 626 while adding the current call to the stack (line 20). Afterwards, it checks if the call occurred in
 627 the SCG (line 21) and hence needs to be iterated on. If the call occurred in the SCG, function
 628 `iterate` updates the cache with the new result (line 24). The operation `Cache.update`
 629 simultaneously updates the cache, widens the new result against an existing entry and checks
 630 if the result is stable or has grown. If the analysis result has grown the function iterates again
 631 (line 25). Otherwise, it removes the call from the SCG and returns the widened result (line 32).
 632 If the SCG consist of only a single element, i.e. the current call, then the current result only
 633 depends on other stable analysis results.

634 To use combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ in a fixpoint algorithm, we need to instantiate it with an
 635 arrow that contains the stack, cache, and SCG:

```
636 Fix stack cache scg a b x y = (x, stack a, cache a b) → (y, cache a b, scg a)
```

640 The arrow type is a function that takes the stack and cache as input and produces the cache
 641 and SCG as output. The types of stack, cache, and SCG are parameters of the arrow to allow
 642 different fixpoint algorithm swapping them out individually. Operations on the stack and
 643 SCGs are self-explanatory. A crucial operation however, is the update of the cache:

```
644 Cache a b = Map a (Stable,b)
645 Cache.update :: Widening b → Fix stack Cache scg a (a,b) (Boolean,b)
646 Cache.update (∇) = proc (call,resnew) → do
647   cache ← Cache.get < ()
648   case Map.lookup call cache of
649     Nothing → do
650       Cache.set < Map.insert call (Unstable,res)
651       return < (True,res)
652     Just (st, resold) → do
653       let reswidened = resold ∇ resnew
654           Cache.set < Map.insert call (if reswidened ⊆ resold then st else Unstable,reswidened)
655       return < (reswidened ⊆ resold, reswidened)
```

659 The cache update widens a prior cached result with the new result. In case the result has
 660 grown, the cache entry is set to `Unstable`. Note, that the update never sets a cache entry to
 661 `Stable`, as this would indicate that the cache entry has reached a global fixpoint and only
 662
 663

664 depends on stable calls, which is not necessarily the case. Cache entries are only set to stable
 665 with operation `Cache.setStable`.

666 To address *Condition 2*, we implement a fixpoint combinator that applies a widening
 667 operator to the current stack and call:
 668

```
669  $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} :: \dots \Rightarrow (\text{stack} \rightarrow a \rightarrow (\text{stack}, a)) \rightarrow c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b$ 
670  $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} \ \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} \ f = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
671   stack  $\leftarrow$  Stack.get  $\prec$  ()
672    $\mathbf{let} \ (\text{stack}_{\text{widened}}, \text{call}_{\text{widened}}) = \text{stack} \ \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} \ \text{call}$ 
673   Stack.local f  $\prec$   $(\text{stack}_{\text{widened}}, \text{call}_{\text{widened}})$ 
674
```

675 Combinator $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$ first accesses the stack contained in the arrow computation. It then
 676 applies the stack widening operator ($\nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}}$) to this stack and current call. Afterwards, it
 677 passes the widened call to the computation `f` and sets the new stack.

678 Lastly, the higher-order fixpoint combinator φ_{filter} , inspired by Wei et al. [50] `fix_select`,
 679 filters out calls not relevant to the rest of the fixpoint algorithm:
 680

```
681  $\varphi_{\text{filter}} :: \dots \Rightarrow (a \rightarrow \text{Boolean}) \rightarrow (c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b) \rightarrow (c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b)$ 
682  $\varphi_{\text{filter}} \ \text{predicate} \ \varphi \ f = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow$ 
683    $\mathbf{if} \ \text{predicate} \ \text{call}$ 
684    $\mathbf{then} \ \varphi \ f \ \prec \ \text{call}$ 
685    $\mathbf{else} \ f \ \prec \ \text{call}$ 
686
```

687 The combinator φ_{filter} either calls the combinator φ whenever the predicate holds, or skips
 688 the combinator φ when the predicate does not hold.

689 With these three fixpoint combinators, we can recreate the fixpoint algorithm `fix_monolithic`
 690 from the previous section:
 691

```
692  $\text{fix}_{\text{monolithic}} = \text{fix}_{\varphi} \ (\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \dots)$ 
693 where  $\varphi = \varphi_{\text{filter}} \ \text{isFunctionBody} \ (\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} \ \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} \circ \varphi_{\text{innermost}})$ 
694
```

695 The execution order of the combinators is from outside inwards: First φ_{filter} gets control,
 696 then $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$, then $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$, and finally $(\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \dots)$ before the cycle repeats.

697 To summarize, in this section we proposed a modular description of fixpoint algorithms.
 698 In particular, we describe fixpoint algorithms with reusable fixpoint combinators, where each
 699 combinator captures a certain aspect of the fixpoint algorithm.
 700

701

702

4 A Library of Reusable Fixpoint Combinators

703 In the previous section, we described a framework for developing modular fixpoint algorithms
 704 by the means of fixpoint combinators. Based on this framework, we develop a library of
 705 reusable fixpoint combinators in this section, which serve as building blocks for fixpoint
 706 algorithms.
 707

708

709

4.1 Iteration Strategy Combinators

710

711

712

713

714

An iteration strategy determines the order in which statements are analyzed. For example, the
 combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ of Section 3 iterates on the innermost SCGs of the graph-shaped trace.
 Furthermore, an iteration strategy cuts off recurrent recursive calls to enforce termination, at
 the cost of precision.

The combinator φ_{topmost} neither requires a stack nor SCGs. Instead, it uses the cache to detect recurrent calls (line 3). On the topmost call of the abstract interpreter, the combinator compares the cache of the current iteration to the cache of the previous iteration (line 22). If the cache of the current iteration has grown, the combinator keeps iterating with a new empty cache (line 26). The `nextIteration` operation additionally widens the call, which allows data like a monotone store to be passed along between iterations.

Mixing iteration strategies. Our case studies show that it is difficult to find a single iteration strategy that works best for all programs (Section 6.2). To this end, the following combinator mixes two iteration strategies φ_1 and φ_2 on a case-by-case basis:

```

777  $\varphi_{\text{alternative}} :: \dots \Rightarrow c \ a \ \text{Boolean} \rightarrow (c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b) \rightarrow (c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b) \rightarrow (c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b)$ 
778  $\varphi_{\text{alternative}} \ \text{predicate} \ \varphi_1 \ \varphi_2 \ f = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
779    $b \leftarrow \text{predicate} \prec \text{call}$ 
780    $\mathbf{if} \ b$ 
781      $\mathbf{then} \ \varphi_1 \ f \prec \text{call}$ 
782      $\mathbf{else} \ \varphi_2 \ f \prec \text{call}$ 
783 
```

The predicate is an effectful computation, which allows it to dynamically adapt the iteration strategy. For example, the predicate may first try both strategies φ_1 and φ_2 once to decide afterwards based on collected performance metrics.

4.2 Recursion Depth Combinators

Recursion depth operators control how deep an abstract interpreter recurses on a program. For example, the combinator $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$ of Section 3 limits the recursion depth to be finite by widening calls on the stack.

Call-site context sensitivity. A popular technique to limit the recursion depth of the abstract interpreter is to join all calls with the same k -truncated call string at the cost of precision [43]. We implement this technique with the following combinator:

```

798 1  $\varphi_{\text{callSiteSensitive}} :: \dots \Rightarrow \text{Int} \rightarrow c \ a \ b \rightarrow c \ a \ b$ 
799 2  $\varphi_{\text{callSiteSensitive}} \ k \ f = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
800 3    $\text{stack} \leftarrow \text{Stack.ask} \prec ()$ 
801 4    $\mathbf{let} \ \text{ctx} = \text{truncate} \ k \ (\text{getLabels} \ \text{stack})$ 
802 5    $\text{call}_{\text{cached}} \leftarrow \text{Context.lookup} \prec \text{ctx}$ 
803 6    $\mathbf{if} \ \text{call} \sqsubseteq \text{call}_{\text{cached}} \ \mathbf{then}$ 
804 7      $f \prec \text{call}_{\text{cached}}$ 
805 8    $\mathbf{else} \ \mathbf{do}$ 
806 9      $\text{call}_{\text{widenend}} \leftarrow \text{Context.update} \prec (\text{ctx}, \text{call})$ 
807 10     $f \prec \text{call}_{\text{widenend}}$ 
808 
```

The combinator $\varphi_{\text{callSiteSensitive}}$ uses a context cache that remembers the call for the current context (line 5). If the context cache contains a larger call than the current call, the combinator calls computation f with the cached call (line 7). Otherwise, the operation `Cache.update` widens the current and cached call and calls computation f with the widened call (line 10). Note that we do not need to change the analysis itself to integrate call-site sensitivity, unlike Shivers [43]. Instead, we simply add this combinator to the fixpoint algorithm.

817 *Stack unfolding.* The following combinator improves precision by unfolding the first few calls
818 on the stack to prevent joining:

```
819  $\varphi_{\text{unfold}} :: \dots \Rightarrow \text{Int} \rightarrow (\text{c a b} \rightarrow \text{c a b}) \rightarrow (\text{c a b} \rightarrow \text{c a b})$ 
820  $\varphi_{\text{unfold}} \text{ limit } \varphi \text{ f} = \mathbf{proc} \text{ call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
821    $n \leftarrow \text{Stack.size} \prec ()$ 
822    $\mathbf{if} \ n \leq \text{limit} \ \mathbf{then} \ \text{f} \prec \text{call}$ 
823    $\mathbf{else} \ \varphi \ \text{f} \prec \text{call} \ \text{-- Stack size exceeds limit}$ 
```

824 The combinator φ_{unfold} recursively calls computation f as long as the stack size is below
825 a certain limit and falls back to the combinator φ if the stack size exceeds the limit. We
826 can integrate this combinator into a fixpoint algorithm by applying it to a stack widening
827 combinator ($\varphi_{\text{unfold}} \ 10 \ (\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} \ \nabla_{\text{Stack}})$). This prevents joining of the stack for the first
828 10 recursive calls.
829

830 *Loop unrolling.* Another common technique to improve precision is to unroll the first few
831 iterations of a loop to prevent joining [28]. Big-step abstract interpreters analyze the same
832 loop statement multiple times recursively:
833

```
834  $\widehat{\text{eval}} = \text{fix}_{\varphi} (\lambda \widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \rightarrow \mathbf{proc} \ \text{statement} \rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ \text{statement} \ \mathbf{of}$ 
835    $\text{WhileLoop} \ \text{condition} \ \text{body} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
836      $\widehat{\text{eval}}_{\text{rec}} \prec \text{If} \ \text{condition} \ (\text{Sequence} \ \text{body} \ (\text{WhileLoop} \ \text{condition} \ \text{body}))$ 
837      $\dots)$ 
```

838 With this observation, we implement a combinator that only joins after the same call appeared
839 a certain number of times on the stack:
840

```
841  $\varphi_{\text{unroll}} :: \dots \Rightarrow \text{Int} \rightarrow (\text{c a b} \rightarrow \text{c a b}) \rightarrow (\text{c a b} \rightarrow \text{c a b})$ 
842  $\varphi_{\text{unroll}} \text{ limit } \varphi \ \text{f} = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
843    $n \leftarrow \text{Stack.getCallCount} \prec \text{call}$ 
844    $\mathbf{if} \ n \leq \text{limit} \ \mathbf{then} \ \mathbf{do}$ 
845      $\text{Stack.incrementCallCount} \prec \text{call}$ 
846      $\text{f} \prec \text{call}$ 
847    $\mathbf{else} \ \varphi \ \text{f} \prec \text{call} \ \text{-- Call count exceeds limit}$ 
```

848 Similar to the previous combinator, we can integrate this combinator by applying it to a stack
849 widening combinator: $\varphi_{\text{unroll}} \ 10 \ (\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} \ \nabla_{\text{Stack}})$
850

851 4.3 Tracing Combinators

852 Tracing combinators run alongside the main fixpoint algorithm to record auxiliary data like a
853 trace, without affecting precision.
854

855 *Recording a control-flow graph.* The following tracing combinator records a control-flow
856 graph (CFG) of the program, which describes the order in which statements are evaluated:
857

```
858  $\varphi_{\text{CFG}} \ \text{f} = \mathbf{proc} \ \text{call} \rightarrow \mathbf{do}$ 
859    $\text{predecessor} \leftarrow \text{getPredecessor} \prec ()$ 
860    $\text{CFG.addEdge} \prec (\text{predecessor}, \text{call})$ 
861    $\text{withNewPredecessor} \ \text{f} \prec \text{call}$ 
```

862 Since the control-flow of a program is encoded implicitly in the big-step abstract interpreter,
863 all the combinator needs to do is to add an edge to the CFG between the most recently
864 evaluated call predecessor and the active call. Afterwards, the combinator passes control
865 to computation f , remembering the active call as new predecessor.
866
867

We can integrate this combinator into an existing fixpoint algorithm by adding it to the front ($\varphi_{\text{CFG}} \circ \varphi_{\text{filter}} \text{isFunctionBody} (\dots \varphi_{\text{innermost}} \dots)$). In this case, the CFG contains all statements as nodes. We can control the granularity of the CFG by changing the position of the φ_{CFG} combinator ($\varphi_{\text{filter}} \text{isFunctionBody} (\varphi_{\text{CFG}} \circ \dots \varphi_{\text{innermost}} \dots)$). In this case, the CFG only contains function calls, in other words, the CFG is an interprocedural call graph.

Debugging static analyses. The following tracing combinator allows debugging of analyses with a graphical debugger [34]:

```

1   $\varphi_{\text{debug}} \text{isBreakpoint } f = \text{proc call} \rightarrow \text{do}$ 
2    if  $\text{isBreakpoint call}$  then do
3       $\text{cfg} \leftarrow \text{CFG.get } \prec ()$ 
4       $\text{stack} \leftarrow \text{Stack.elems } \prec ()$ 
5       $\text{command} \leftarrow \text{Client.send } \prec (\text{call}, \text{cfg}, \text{stack})$ 
6      case  $\text{command}$  of
7         $\text{Step} \rightarrow \text{breakAtNextStatement } \prec ()$ 
8        ...
9     $f \prec \text{call}$ 

```

The fixpoint combinator runs as a server within the fixpoint algorithm and sends information to a graphical debugging client in a browser. On a break point the combinator sends the current stack and the CFG to the debugging client (line 5). After the client returned a debugging command, the combinator executes the command and calls computation f . This resumes the analysis until the combinator hits the next break point.

5 Modular Soundness Proofs of Big-Step Fixpoint Algorithms

In this section, we develop a formal theory to prove soundness of big-step fixpoint algorithms that consist of fixpoint combinators. In particular, we prove that a modular fixpoint algorithm is sound if all of its combinators are sound.

To this end, we first review a soundness proof of monolithic fixpoint algorithms, which we later extend for modular algorithms:

PROPOSITION 5.1 (SOUNDNESS OF MONOLITHIC FIXPOINT ALGORITHMS [8]). *Let $\widehat{\text{eval}} : \widehat{D} \rightarrow \widehat{D}$ be an abstract interpreter and $\text{eval} : D \rightarrow D$ be the monotone collecting semantics of the concrete interpreter over two complete lattices $(\widehat{D}, \sqsubseteq, \perp)$ and (D, \sqsubseteq, \perp) . Furthermore, let $\gamma : \widehat{D} \rightarrow D$ be a monotone concretization function such that $\forall x \in D. \widehat{x} \in \widehat{D}. x \sqsubseteq \gamma(\widehat{x}) \implies \text{eval}(x) \sqsubseteq \gamma(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{x}))$. A fixpoint algorithm for the abstract interpreter is sound if it yields a post-fixpoint of $\widehat{\text{eval}}$, i.e. an element $\widehat{p} \in \widehat{D}$ with $\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p}) \sqsubseteq \widehat{p}$.*

PROOF.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p}) \sqsubseteq \widehat{p} & (\widehat{p} \text{ is a post-fixpoint of } \widehat{\text{eval}}) \\
\implies \gamma(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p})) \sqsubseteq \gamma(\widehat{p}) & (\gamma \text{ is monotone}) \\
\implies \text{eval}(\gamma(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p}))) \sqsubseteq \gamma(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p})) & (\widehat{\text{eval}} \text{ sound w.r.t. eval}) \\
\implies \text{lfp}(\text{eval}) \sqsubseteq \gamma(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\widehat{p})) & (\text{Tarski's fixpoint theorem [47]} \quad \square)
\end{array}$$

This proposition requires that the collecting semantics of the concrete interpreter is monotone, such that the least fixpoint $\text{lfp}(\text{eval})$ exists. Monotonicity of the collecting

919 semantics follows directly by Scott-continuity of the denotational semantics of the concrete
920 interpreter [46].

921 We build on this idea to develop a soundness composition theorem for modular big-step
922 fixpoint algorithms. Let us first assume that the modular fixpoint algorithm is built from
923 fixpoint combinators over the following grammar:
924

925 $\varphi ::= \varphi$ atomic	(atomic combinators)
926 $\quad \varphi \circ \varphi$	(combinator composition)
927 $\quad \varphi(\varphi \dots \varphi)$	(higher-order combinators)

929 This grammar allows us to formulate the following soundness lemmas for each type of
930 combinator:
931

932 atomic φ sound	if \forall monotone \widehat{f} . $\forall \widehat{x}$. $\varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \implies \widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$
933 $\varphi_1 \circ \varphi_2$ sound	if φ_1 sound \wedge φ_2 sound
934 higher-order φ sound	if $\forall \varphi_1 \dots \varphi_n$. φ_1 sound $\wedge \dots \wedge \varphi_n$ sound 935 $\implies \varphi(\varphi_1 \dots \varphi_n)$ sound

936 That is, an atomic fixpoint combinator φ is sound if all post-fixpoints of $\varphi \circ \widehat{f}$ are also
937 post-fixpoints of \widehat{f} , for any \widehat{f} . All other types of combinator preserve this post-fixpoint
938 property.

939 These soundness lemmas allow us to prove soundness of modular fixpoint algorithms once
940 and for all with the following theorem:
941

942 **THEOREM 5.2 (SOUNDNESS OF MODULAR FIXPOINT ALGORITHMS).** *A modular fixpoint*
943 *algorithm $\text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})$ is sound, if all of its combinators φ are sound.*
944

945 **PROOF.** We prove by structural induction over φ that $\forall \widehat{f}, \widehat{x}$. $\varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \implies \widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$.
946 By definition of fix , we get $\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}}(\text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}}))) = \text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})$, which satisfies the
947 precondition above. We conclude $\widehat{\text{eval}}(\text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})) \sqsubseteq \text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})$, which shows that
948 $\text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})$ is a post-fixpoint of $\widehat{\text{eval}}$. Thus the fixpoint algorithm $\text{fix}_\varphi(\widehat{\text{eval}})$ is sound by
949 Proposition 5.1. □

950 This way of proving soundness of modular fixpoint algorithms is more flexible than a
951 monolithic proof because it allows us to reorder and add new combinators without invalidating
952 the soundness proof.
953

954 5.1 Soundness Proof Strategies for Fixpoint Combinators

955 In this subsection, we prove three theorems that guarantee soundness of three classes of
956 combinators. The soundness proofs are split into two parts: One part proves soundness of
957 classes of combinators that satisfy certain properties (Theorem 5.3 and 5.4) and one part
958 shows combinator implementations actually satisfy these properties (Corollary 5.4 and 5.6).
959

960 *Extensive Fixpoint Combinators.* A fixpoint combinator φ is extensive iff for all monotone \widehat{f}
961 and for all \widehat{x} , it holds $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$. This is the case if $\varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \prec a$ calls $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec a'$ with a
962 greater argument $a' \sqsupseteq a$ such that $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec a \sqsubseteq \widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec a' \sqsubseteq \varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \prec a$.
963
964
965
966
967
968
969

970 THEOREM 5.3. *An extensive fixpoint combinator φ is sound.*

971 PROOF. We assume $\varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$ for all monotone \widehat{f} and for all \widehat{x} . By extensivity, we conclude
 972 $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$. □

973 COROLLARY 5.4. *Combinators $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}$ and φ_{CFG} are sound.*

974 PROOF. By Theorem 5.3 it suffices to show that the combinators are extensive. Combinator
 975 $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}(\nabla_{\text{Stack}})(\widehat{f})$ is extensive because it calls \widehat{f} with an upper bound of the current
 976 input. Calling $\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}(\nabla_{\text{Stack}})(\widehat{f})$ is greater than just calling \widehat{f} by monotonicity of \widehat{f} .
 977 Hence it follows $\widehat{f} \sqsubseteq \varphi_{\text{stackWiden}}(\nabla_{\text{Stack}})(\widehat{f})$. Combinator $\varphi_{\text{CFG}}(\widehat{f})$ is extensive because it
 978 calls function \widehat{f} with the same argument it was supplied with. □

979 *Interleaving Fixpoint Combinators.* A higher-order fixpoint combinator $\varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$
 980 is interleaving iff $\varphi_1(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$ or $\varphi_2(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$. This is the
 981 case if φ either calls combinator φ_1 or calls combinator φ_2 . This observation leads us to our
 982 second theorem:

983 THEOREM 5.5 (SOUNDNESS OF INTERLEAVING FIXPOINT COMBINATORS). *Let φ be a higher-*
 984 *order fixpoint combinator, such that for all φ_1, φ_2 , it holds $\forall x. \varphi_1(x) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(x) \vee$*
 985 *$\varphi_2(x) \sqsubseteq \varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(x)$, then φ is sound.*

986 PROOF. We assume $\varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$ for a given \widehat{f}, \widehat{x} . We assume that both φ_1 and
 987 φ_2 are sound by the soundness definition of the higher-order combinator φ . If $\varphi_1(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq$
 988 $\varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$, then $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$ follows immediately by soundness of φ_1 . The other case is
 989 analogous. □

990 COROLLARY 5.6. *The combinators $\varphi_{\text{alternative}}$, φ_{filter} and φ_{unroll} are sound by Theo-*
 991 *rem 5.5.*

992 PROOF. By Theorem 5.5, it suffices to show that the combinators are interleaving. The
 993 combinator $\varphi_{\text{alternative}}(P, \varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$ either calls $\varphi_1(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$ or $\varphi_2(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$ depending
 994 on the predicate P . Hence $\varphi_1(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \varphi_{\text{alternative}}(P, \varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$ or $\varphi_2(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq$
 995 $\varphi_{\text{alternative}}(P, \varphi_1, \varphi_2)(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}))$. Furthermore, combinator φ_{filter} is interleaving because
 996 $\varphi_{\text{filter}}(P, \varphi_1) = \varphi_{\text{alternative}}(P, \varphi_1, \varphi_{\text{id}})$, where $\varphi_{\text{id}}(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \prec a = \widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec a$ is the identity
 997 combinator. Finally, φ_{unroll} is interleaving because $\varphi_{\text{unroll}}(n, \varphi_2) = \varphi_{\text{alternative}}(P_n, \varphi_{\text{id}}, \varphi_2)$,
 998 where predicate P_n is true after n recursive calls. □

999 *Cache-Based Fixpoint Combinators.* Lastly, we prove soundness of the cache-based fixpoint
 1000 combinators like $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$:

1001 THEOREM 5.7. *The fixpoint combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ is sound.*

1002 PROOF. We assume $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}(\widehat{f}(\widehat{x})) \sqsubseteq \widehat{x}$ for all monotone \widehat{f} and for all \widehat{x} and call.

1003 The key insight is that unstable intermediate results only occur within SCGs and $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$
 1004 does not return until all calls within the SCG have reached a post-fixpoint. To this end, we
 1005 first prove that either $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec \text{call} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$ or that the `call` appears on the stack and in
 1006 the resulting SCG set.

- 1007 • If `resultcached` is unstable and the `call` does not occur on the stack, combinator
 1008 $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ iterates until `resultnew` does not grow anymore (line 25 in $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$) and
 1009 `resultnew` \sqsubseteq `resultcached`. In this case, combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ removes the call from
 1010

1021 the SCG set and returns $\text{result}_{\text{widened}}$ (line 32). By the assumption, it follows that
 1022 $\text{return} \prec \text{result}_{\text{widened}} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$. By transitivity we conclude $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec \text{call} \sqsubseteq$
 1023 $\text{return} \prec \text{result}_{\text{new}} \sqsubseteq \text{return} \prec \text{result}_{\text{widened}} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$.

- 1024 • If $\text{result}_{\text{cached}}$ is unstable and the call occurs on the stack, combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ adds
 1025 the call to the SCG (line 10).
- 1026 • If $\text{result}_{\text{cached}}$ is stable, combinator $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ simply returns the cached result (line
 1027 6). By the assumption, it follows that $\text{return} \prec \text{result}_{\text{cached}} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$. Furthermore,
 1028 the `Cache.update` operation only marks a result as stable if $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec \text{call} \sqsubseteq \text{return} \prec$
 1029 $\text{result}_{\text{cached}}$, as explained in the previous case. By transitivity we conclude $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec \text{call} \sqsubseteq$
 1030 $\text{return} \prec \text{result}_{\text{cached}} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$.

1032 When we run a fixpoint algorithm including $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$, we initialize the stack to be empty.
 1033 This means that `call` cannot appear on the stack and hence $\widehat{f}(\widehat{x}) \prec \text{call} \sqsubseteq \widehat{x} \prec \text{call}$ has to
 1034 be true. □

1036 **THEOREM 5.8.** *The fixpoint combinator $\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$ is sound.*

1037 **PROOF.** The argument for $\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$ is similar to $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$. The only difference is that
 1038 $\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$ waits until the SCG contains only a single element. But this does not change that
 1039 it only returns from an SCG until all calls within reached a post-fixpoint. □

1042 To summarize, in this section we presented a way to prove soundness of fixpoint algorithms
 1043 that consist of fixpoint combinators. In particular, a fixpoint algorithm is sound, if all of
 1044 its combinators are sound. This simplifies the soundness proof, as it suffices to prove each
 1045 combinator sound individually. Furthermore, we proved soundness of three classes of fixpoint
 1046 combinators.

1048 6 Case Studies

1049 In this section, we evaluate the feasibility of our framework for modular fixpoint algorithms.
 1050 In particular, we integrated the combinators of Section 4 into the Sturdy library [18, 22] and
 1051 used them to develop fixpoint algorithms for the following analyses:

- 1052 • A static type analysis [19] for Stratego [49], a domain-specific dynamically-typed language
 1053 for program transformations,
- 1054 • a k -CFA [43] for Scheme [1], a dynamically-typed programming language with first-class
 1055 functions and mutable state.

1057 The goal of these case studies is to assess the language and analysis independence, the precision
 1058 and the performance of the fixpoint combinators.

1061 6.1 Static Type Analysis for Stratego

1062 In our first case study, we implemented a fixpoint algorithm for a static type analysis [19]
 1063 for Stratego [49], a domain-specific dynamically-typed language for developing program
 1064 transformations. Stratego is difficult to type statically because of features like generic program
 1065 traversals that temporarily produce ill-sorted programs.

1066 The abstract interpreter takes a Stratego program called a *strategy*, a strategy environment,
 1067 a term environment, and a program term that is to be transformed. Furthermore, the abstract
 1068 interpreter returns as output a list of errors, an updated term environment and a resulting
 1069 term.

1071

1072 $\widehat{\text{eval}} :: \dots \Rightarrow c (\text{Strategy}, \widehat{\text{StratEnv}}, \widehat{\text{TermEnv}}, \widehat{\text{Term}}) (\widehat{\text{Errors}}, \widehat{\text{Either}} () (\widehat{\text{TermEnv}}, \widehat{\text{Term}}))$
 1073 $\widehat{\text{eval}} = \text{fix}_{(\varphi_{\text{filter}} \text{ isStrategyBody } (\varphi_{\text{stackWiden}} \nabla_{\widehat{\text{Stack}}} \circ \varphi_{\text{outermost}}))} \dots$

1074 If the strategy fails to match a term pattern, the abstract interpreter returns the empty tuple
 1075 instead. Type-checking Stragego program transformations is not trivial since generic program
 1076 traversals may produce intermediate terms that are ill-sorted. To solve this, the analysis uses
 1077 an abstract domain that is able to represent ill-sorted terms:
 1078

1079 $\widehat{\text{Term}} = \text{Sorted Sort} \mid \text{MaybeSorted } \mathcal{P}(\text{Constructor}, \widehat{\text{Term}})$

1080 This abstract domain is infinite since abstract terms can grow infinitely deep. To this end, a
 1081 widening operator cuts-off terms at a specified depth, trying to type check deeper terms to
 1082 determine their sort.
 1083

1084 The fixpoint algorithm uses the outermost iteration strategy and applies a stack widening
 1085 operator because the abstract term domain and term environment are infinite. The stack
 1086 widening operator replaces the current call with the topmost call on the stack that is greater.
 1087 To debug the analysis during development we added a tracing combinator φ_{trace} within the
 1088 φ_{filter} expression to print a trace of analyzed strategies and their abstract term arguments.
 1089 Furthermore, we occasionally moved the tracing combinator to the outside of the φ_{filter}
 1090 expression for a more fine grained trace that contains all substrategies as well.
 1091

1092 We tested the abstract interpreter and its fixpoint algorithm on a test suite with 61 test
 1093 cases including 3 existing program transformations: a desugaring of arrows (665 lines of
 1094 code)⁷ [32], a normalization of arrows to causal commutative normal form (490 loc) [27],
 1095 and an interpreter for PCF (61 loc) [33]. We found that in all of these test cases the abstract
 1096 interpreter terminates with a sound analysis result. Furthermore, the results were precise
 1097 enough to validate the well-typedness of the 3 program transformations.

1098 This case study shows that the modular fixpoint algorithm is precise enough to yield usable
 1099 analysis results.
 1100

1101 6.2 *k-CFA for Scheme*

1102 For our second case study, we implemented an inter-procedural control-flow analysis
 1103 (*k-CFA*) [43] and static type analysis for Scheme [1], a dynamically-typed real-world
 1104 programming language with first-class functions and mutable state. The abstract interpreter
 1105 takes as input a list of expressions, an environment, store and errors and returns as output an
 1106 abstract value, store and errors:
 1107

1108 $\widehat{\text{Env}} = \text{Map String } \widehat{\text{Addr}} \quad \widehat{\text{Store}} = \text{Map } \widehat{\text{Addr}} \widehat{\text{Val}} \quad \widehat{\text{Errors}} = \mathcal{P}(\text{String})$

1110 $\widehat{\text{eval}} :: \dots \Rightarrow c ([\text{Expr}], \widehat{\text{Env}}, \widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Errors}}) (\widehat{\text{Val}}, \widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Errors}})$

1111 $\widehat{\text{eval}} = \text{fix}_{(\varphi_{\text{filter}} \text{ isApplication } (\varphi_{\text{recordCallSite}} k) \circ \varphi_{\text{filter}} \text{ isFunctionBody } \varphi_{\text{topmost}})} \dots$

1112 The abstract domain includes a set-based abstraction for closures and quoted symbols, a
 1113 shape abstraction for lists, a constant abstraction for booleans, and type-based abstraction for
 1114 all other datatypes:
 1115

1116 $\widehat{\text{Val}} = \top \mid \text{ClosureVal } (\mathcal{P}(\text{Expr}, \widehat{\text{Env}})) \mid \text{ListVal } \widehat{\text{List}} \mid \text{BoolVal } \widehat{\text{Bool}} \mid \text{NumVal } \widehat{\text{Num}} \mid \dots$

1117 $\widehat{\text{List}} = \text{Nil} \mid \text{Cons } \mathcal{P}(\widehat{\text{Addr}}) \mathcal{P}(\widehat{\text{Addr}}) \mid \text{NilOrCons } \mathcal{P}(\widehat{\text{Addr}}) \mathcal{P}(\widehat{\text{Addr}})$

1118 $\widehat{\text{Bool}} = \top \mid \text{True} \mid \text{False}$

1119 $\widehat{\text{Num}} = \top \mid \text{IntVal} \mid \text{FloatVal}$

1120

1121 ⁷Counted with `wc -l` because the standard tool `cloc` does not support Stragego code.

1122

Even though Scheme is a dynamically-typed language, the abstract domain above is typically used for statically-typed languages. Specifically, two abstract values of different types join to \top . This choice of abstract domain is precise enough to soundly compute the control-flow of all but one benchmark program we discuss below, but performs better than a set-based abstraction.

We first developed an initial fixpoint algorithm that we later specialize. The initial fixpoint algorithm uses φ_{topmost} as a baseline iteration strategy because it does not compute SCGs similar to Shivers's k -CFA. Furthermore, the algorithm uses the combinator $\varphi_{\text{recordCallSite}}$ to record the k most recent call sites, which we use as abstract addresses.

While the initial fixpoint algorithm terminates and is sound, the algorithm “forgets” about recent store and error updates when it returns a cached result. To address this problem, we specialize the fixpoint algorithm to use a different cache that respects the part of the input and output that only ever grows. The following code shows the lookup operation of the cache:

```

Cache.lookup :: ... => c (a,s) (Stable,(b,s))           MonotoneCache a b m =
Cache.lookup = proc (call,monotonenew) -> do         Map a (Stable,b,m)
  cache ← getCache < ()
  if call ∈ cache then do
    let (stableold,result,monotoneold) = cache(call)
        let stable = if monotoneold ⊆ monotonenew then stableold else Unstable
        return < (stable, (result, monotonenew))
    else return < (Unstable, (⊥, monotonenew))

```

The lookup operation of $\widehat{\text{MonotoneCache}}$ always returns the new and greater element $\text{monotone}_{\text{new}}$. The cached element $\text{monotone}_{\text{old}}$ is only kept to determine if the result is stable. Returning the old cached element $\text{monotone}_{\text{old}}$ would forget about the store and error updates.

We integrate this improvement into the initial fixpoint algorithm by replacing the cache that is contained in the arrow computation. Furthermore, we use the combinator $\varphi_{\text{transform}}$ to group the parts of the input and output that grow monotonically:

```

 $\varphi_{\text{transform}} [([\text{Expr}], \widehat{\text{Env}}, \widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Errors}}) \simeq ([[\text{Expr}], \widehat{\text{Env}}], (\widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Errors}}))]
[\widehat{\text{Val}}, \widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Error}}] \simeq [\widehat{\text{Val}}, (\widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Error}})]
(\varphi_{\text{filter isApplication}} (\varphi_{\text{recordCallSite}} k) \circ \varphi_{\text{filter isFunctionBody}} \varphi_{\text{topmost}})$ 

```

The combinator $\varphi_{\text{transform}}$ applies two isomorphisms to the inputs and outputs of the abstract interpreter such that variable `call` has type $([\text{Expr}], \widehat{\text{Env}})$ and variable `monotonenew` has type $(\widehat{\text{Store}}, \widehat{\text{Error}})$ within the `Cache.lookup` operation above.

We evaluate 3 different iteration strategies by analyzing Scheme programs of the *Gabriel* [12] and *Scala-AM* benchmark suite [11]. The *Gabriel* benchmark suite contains 9 Scheme files from 17 up to 562 lines of code (loc) with an average of 137 loc.⁸ The *Scala-AM* benchmark suite contains 5 Scheme files from 10 up to 40 loc with an average of 26 loc. The analysis is precise enough to soundly analyze the control-flow of all benchmark programs, except for *dderiv* where the analysis tries to call a closure that is \top .

Figure 2 shows the speedups over the baseline iteration strategy φ_{topmost} of our initial fixpoint algorithm. Benchmarks like *cpstak* and *diviter* have an SCG at the very top of the program. This means there is no significant difference between the iteration orders and the overhead of computing the SCGs slows down the iteration strategies $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ and

⁸Counted with `cloc` (<https://github.com/AIDanial/cloc>).

Fig. 2. Absolute (top) and normalized running times (bottom) of different iteration strategies for a OCFA analysis for Scheme. The bottom plot shows the speedup of each iteration strategy over the baseline φ_{topmost} (higher is better).

$\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$. On other benchmarks like *destruct*, *takl*, and *rsa* the SCGs are smaller and do not span the entire program. In these cases the iteration strategies $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ and $\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$ get an considerable speedup. The results show that no single iteration strategy performs best for all analyzed programs and further fine-tuning is needed.

Lastly, we assess the potential performance overhead caused by the modularization of the fixpoint algorithm. In particular, we inspected the low-level code of the fixpoint algorithm generated by the Haskell compiler GHC. The GHC compiler first inlines the definitions of the fixpoint combinators and arrow computation and then optimizes the residual code. The result is a pure function close to a hand-written monolithic fixpoint algorithm, meaning that modularization has no performance penalty.

To summarize, the k -CFA case study demonstrates three points:

- We were able to specialize the initial fixpoint algorithm without changing code of existing fixpoint combinators.
- We compared the performance of 3 different iteration strategies and concluded that no iteration strategy performs best for all programs.
- The Haskell compiler optimizes the modularized fixpoint algorithm by inlining and produces code close to hand-written monolithic fixpoint algorithm. Thus, modularization does not inflict a performance penalty.

7 Stack-Based Fixpoint Algorithms in Scala

Since the publication of our original ICFP paper [20], we have migrated the Sturdy analysis framework from Haskell to Scala [5]. In the process, we also had a chance to redesign the implementation of the combinator-based fixpoint algorithms. The new design puts a fixpoint stack at the architectural center: Iteration strategies use the stack to implement their iteration schemes, and fixpoint combinators compose and configure iteration strategies. Our new central fixpoint stack subsumes the stack, cache, and strongly-connected subgraphs (SCGs) from the Haskell implementation. While this makes for a slightly less flexible design, we believe it helps the understandability and usability of our fixpoint algorithms.

7.1 Iteration Strategies

In this subsection, we first revisit the innermost, outermost, and topmost iteration strategies and present their implementation in Scala.

```

1241 1 def  $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ [A,B](stack: Stack[A, B]): Combinator[A,B] = new Innermost[A,B](stack)
1242 2
1243 3 class Innermost[A,B](stack: Stack[A, B]) extends Combinator[A,B]:
1244 4   override def apply(f: A => B): A => B =
1245 5     @tailrec
1246 6     def iterate(call: A): B =
1247 7       stack.push(call) match
1248 8         case PushResult.Skip(result) => result.getOrElse(throw RecurrentCall(call))
1249 9         case PushResult.Continue(callwidened) =>
1250 10          val result = f(callwidened)
1251 11          stack.pop(callwidened, result) match
1252 12            case PopResult.Stable(entry) =>
1253 13              if (!stack.hasRecurrentCalls) entry.stable = Stability.Stable
1254 14              entry.result
1255 15            case PopResult.Unstable(resultwidened) =>
1256 16              iterate(call)
1257 17   iterate

```

Listing 3. Innermost Combinator in Scala

Innermost. The innermost iteration strategy computes the fixpoint of a recursive call as soon as it occurs. We can describe this strategy as a fixpoint combinator in Scala (Listing 3).⁹

As in Haskell, a fixpoint combinator `Combinator[A,B]` is a function $(A \Rightarrow B) \Rightarrow A \Rightarrow B$. Given function `f`, `Innermost` computes its fixpoint using an auxiliary tail-recursive function `iterate: A => B`. First, we push the current call on the stack (Line 7). If the stack indicates a `Skip`, we yield the cached result or `throw` a `RecurrentCall`, which is a bottom element of the abstract domain. If instead the stack indicates a `Continue`, we run `f` to obtain out. We then `pop` the current call from the stack (Line 11). If the stack indicates that the call produced a `Stable` result, we need to check if the call was the outermost recurrent call. Only then can we guarantee that the result is permanently stable, in exact correspondence with the check `sizeSCG == 1` that we saw in the Haskell definition of $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$. Lastly, if

⁹We name all Scala fixpoint combinators with ϕ to distinguish them from Haskell combinators with φ .

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1276 the fixpoint stack indicates the result is `Unstable`, we know it is recursive and compute its
 1277 fixpoint immediately.

```

1278
1279 // Parameter A represents the inputs and B the outputs of the abstract interpreter
1280 trait Stack[A,B]:
1281   def push(call: A): PushResult
1282   def pop(call: A, result: B): PopResult
1283
1284   enum PushResult:
1285     case Skip(result: Option[B]) // call is cached or recurrent, skip it
1286     case Continue(call: A)      // call activated, state may have been widened
1287
1288   enum PopResult:
1289     case Stable(e: CacheEntry) // result did not change, iteration may end
1290     case Unstable(result: B)  // result changed, iteration must continue
1291
1292   /** Mutable fields allow in-place updates. */
1293   class CacheEntry(var result: B, var stable: Stability)
1294   enum Stability:
1295     case Stable
1296     case Unstable
  
```

1297 Listing 4. Scala’s fixpoint stack interface combines Haskell’s stack, cache, and SCG interfaces
 1298
 1299

1300 Scala’s `Stack` interface combines Haskell’s interfaces for the stack, cache, and SCG into
 1301 one. We will discuss its implementation in more detail in [Section 7.2](#). Compared to the
 1302 Haskell definition of $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$, using the `Stack` in Scala’s $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ halved the lines of code
 1303 required for its implementation. More importantly, `Stack` also shielded us from concerning
 1304 multiple technical aspects. Specifically, $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ interacts with components that manage
 1305 the stack, cache and SCG in intricate ways. In contrast, `Innermost` only needs to interact
 1306 with `Stack` and its simple push/pop interface.
 1307

1308 *Outermost and topmost.* We can define different iteration strategies on top of `Stack`. In
 1309 contrast to what we saw in Haskell, the iteration strategies defined with `Stack` share a very
 1310 similar structure: They first push then pop the current call, unless the push is skipped. The
 1311 main difference is *when* to iterate by calling `iterate` recursively. In $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ we iterated
 1312 as soon as we found a new recursive call. In contrast, $\phi_{\text{outermost}}$ and ϕ_{topmost} defer iteration
 1313 until reaching the outermost recursive call or the topmost interpreter call, respectively. We can
 1314 subsume both strategies in a single combinator `OutsideMost` that is parametric in `isOutside`
 1315 ([Listing 5](#)). The structure of `iterate` largely coincides with `Innermost`, with two notable
 1316 differences. First, we introduce an abstract method `isOutside` that allows subclasses to
 1317 indicate where to iterate. Combinator $\phi_{\text{outermost}}$ iterates when the last recurrent call on the
 1318 stack is popped. Combinator ϕ_{topmost} iterates when the stack is empty at the entry point of
 1319 the program. Second, to delay iteration, we introduce a variable (Line 10) to remember if any
 1320 iteration is necessary. An iteration is necessary if we ever encounter an unstable recursive
 1321 call (Line 23), where we yield the widened output rather than iterating immediately as in
 1322 $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$. After each pop, if an iteration is necessary and we are at the outside-most call
 1323 (Line 25), we reset the variable `isLooping` and iterate. Again, `Stack` allowed us to implement
 1324
 1325
 1326

```

1327 1 def  $\phi_{\text{outermost}}$ [A,B](stack:Stack[A,B]):Combinator[A,B] = new OutsideMost[A,B](stack):
1328 2   override def isOutside: Boolean = !stack.hasRecurrentCalls
1329 3
1330 4 def  $\phi_{\text{topmost}}$ [A,B](stack:Stack[A,B]):Combinator[A,B] = new OutsideMost[A,B](stack):
1331 5   override def isOutside: Boolean = stack.height == 0
1332 6
1333 7 trait OutsideMost[A, B](val stack: FixStack[A, B]) extends Combinator[A, B]:
1334 8   def isOutside: Boolean
1335 9   override def apply(f: A => B): A => B =
1336 10     var isLooping = false
1337 11     @tailrec
1338 12     def iterate(call: A): B =
1339 13       val result = stack.push(call) match
1340 14         case PushResult.Skip(result) => out.getOrElse(throw RecurrentCall(result))
1341 15         case PushResult.Continue(callwidened) =>
1342 16           val result = f(callwidened)
1343 17           val recurrentBefore = stack.hasRecurrentCalls
1344 18           stack.pop(callwidened, result) match
1345 19             case PopResult.Stable(entry) =>
1346 20               if (isOutside && !isLooping) entry.stable = Stability.Stable
1347 21               entry.result
1348 22             case PopResult.Unstable(resultwidened) =>
1349 23               isLooping = true
1350 24               resultwidened
1351 25           if (isLooping && isOutside)
1352 26             isLooping = false
1353 27             iterate(call)
1354 28           else
1355 29             result
1356 30     iterate

```

Listing 5. Outermost and Topmost Combinators in Scala

iteration strategies in fewer lines of code, and without interacting with the cache or SCGs directly.

7.2 Fixpoint Stack

We now describe the implementation of the fixpoint stack in more detail. The new fixpoint stack subsumes the stack, cache, and strongly-connected subgraphs (SCGs) from the Haskell implementation.

We show the full implementation of the fixpoint stack in [Figure 3](#). The fixpoint stack uses three essential data structures to maintain its state.

- (1) `stack: Map[A, Int]` represents the call stack: it contains all active calls and the index of their position on the stack. The fixpoint algorithm identifies an active call by the state of the abstract interpreter `A`. The stack representation is equivalent to a more conventional representation `List[A]`, because each call can only be active once at the same time. Instead, the map datastructure supports the detection of recurrent calls that are already active.

```

1378 1 class FixStack[A,B](stackWidening:StackWiden[A], resultWidening:Widen[B]) extends
1379   Stack[A,B]:
1380 2   /** Active calls identified by their state and stack position. */
1381 3   private val stack: mutable.Map[A, B] = mutable.Map()
1382 4   /** Corecurrent calls: Active calls that have been recursively called. */
1383 5   private val corecurrentCalls: mutable.Set[Int] = mutable.BitSet()
1384 6   /** Cache of previously executed corecurrent calls and their output. */
1385 7   private val cache: mutable.Map[A, CacheEntry] = mutable.Map()
1386 8   def height: Int = stack.size
1387 9   def hasRecurrentCalls: Boolean = corecurrentCalls.nonEmpty
1388 10
1389 11 def push(call: A): PushResult =
1390 12   val callwidened = stackWidening.push(call)
1391 13   stack.get(callwidened) match
1392 14     case None => // call is not recurrent, return stable cache entry if it exists
1393 15     cache.get(callwidened) match
1394 16       case Some(entry) if entry.stable == Stability.Stable =>
1395 17         stackWidening.pop(call)
1396 18         return PushResult.Skip(Some(entry.result))
1397 19     case _ => // no stable cache entry found
1398 20     stack.put(callwidened, stack.size) // push call to stack
1399 21     PushResult.Continue(callwidened) // continue with widened input state
1400 22 case Some(corecurPos) => // recurrent, given the original stack position
1401 23   corecurrentCalls += corecurPos // register corecurrent call
1402 24   stackWidening.pop(call)
1403 25   cache.get(callwidened) match // yield previous result if it exists
1404 26     case Some(CacheEntry(result, _)) => PushResult.Skip(Some(result))
1405 27     case None => PushResult.Skip(None) // iteration must start with ⊥
1406 28
1407 29 def pop(call: A, result: B): PopResult =
1408 30   stackWidening.pop(call) // pop call from stack
1409 31   stack.remove(call)
1410 32   val isCorecurrent = corecurrentCalls.remove(stack.size)
1411 33   if (isCorecurrent) storeCorecurrentResult(call, result)
1412 34   else PopResult.Stable(new CacheEntry(result, Stability.Unstable))
1413 35
1414 36 private def storeCorecurrentResult(call: A, result: B): PopResult =
1415 37   cache.get(call) match
1416 38     case None => // first result for in, always considered unstable
1417 39     cache.put(call, new CacheEntry(result, Stability.Unstable))
1418 40     PopResult.Unstable(result)
1419 41     case Some(entry) =>
1420 42     resultWidening(entry.result, result) match
1421 43       case Changed(resultwidened) =>
1422 44         entry.result = resultwidened
1423 45         PopResult.Unstable(resultwidened)
1424 46       case Unchanged =>
1425 47         PopResult.Stable(entry)
1426
1427
1428

```

Fig. 3. Fixpoint stack in Scala, subsuming the stack, cache, and SCG from Haskell.

- 1429 (2) `corecurrentCalls`: `Set[Int]` represents the subset of active calls that have been called
 1430 recurrently. When a call is popped, the fixpoint algorithm checks if it is corecurrent in
 1431 order to apply widening and compare to the cached results.
- 1432 (3) `cache`: `Map[A, CacheEntry]` represents the cache of previously computed results. A
 1433 cache entry can be stable or unstable, indicating whether further fixpoint iterations are
 1434 necessary. Eventually, all cache entries will be stable if the iteration strategy is correct.
 1435

1436 The `push` method takes the state of an analysis call and either instructs the iteration
 1437 strategy to `PushResult.Continue` or `PushResult.Skip`. A `Skip` then occurs when (i) a
 1438 stable result for `call` exists in the cache (Line 18) or (ii) `call` is a recurrent call to the
 1439 corecurrent call at position `corecPos` (Line 22). For recurrent calls, the `push` registers the
 1440 corecurrent call and query the cache for a prior result. Initially, recurrent calls yield `None`,
 1441 which indicates a \perp result to the iteration strategy. Subsequently, the iteration strategy will
 1442 proceed toward a fixpoint by reusing the previously computed results for recurrent calls.
 1443 When a call is neither cached nor recurrent, method `push` adds it to the stack and indicates
 1444 that the iteration strategy should `Continue` analyzing the call (Line 21). Finally, note that
 1445 `push` uses `stackWidening`, which exactly corresponds to ∇_{Stack} from Section 2.2. When a
 1446 `Skip` occurs, it is important to pop the call from the stack widening, because there won't be
 1447 an explicit invocation of the `pop` method.
 1448

1449 The `pop` method must be called whenever `push` instructed a `Continue`. Method `pop` takes
 1450 the original analysis call and its analysis result. First, `pop` then removes `call` from the
 1451 stack and the stack widening. Method `pop` then checks if `call` is a corecurrent call (Line 32),
 1452 which is the case if its stack position `stack.size` has been registered in `push` (Line 23). For
 1453 corecurrent calls, `pop` checks and updates the cache in `storeCorecurrentResult`. Otherwise,
 1454 it yields `PopResult.Stable` with a dummy cache entry. By yielding `PopResult.Stable`,
 1455 `pop` indicates that the current analysis call `call` does not require iteration itself, although it
 1456 may transitively depend on analysis results, which are not stable yet. The iteration strategy
 1457 must update the stability field of the returned cache entry whenever it finalized the fixpoint of
 1458 an analysis call. However, for calls that are not corecurrent, `pop` yields a dummy cache entry
 1459 since it does not cache its result anyways.
 1460

1461 Lastly, the `storeCorecurrentResult` method checks if `call` already has a cache entry
 1462 and if that entry changed. If there is no cache entry yet, `storeCorecurrentResult` adds an
 1463 entry and yields `PopResult.Unstable`, because it cannot confirm that the result is stable
 1464 (Line 40). If there is a cache entry, `storeCorecurrentResult` widens the old and the new
 1465 results (Line 42). The widening operator also indicates if the result changed. If it changed,
 1466 `storeCorecurrentResult` updates the cache entry and indicates an `Unstable` result. If it
 1467 did not change, `storeCorecurrentResult` indicates a `Stable` result with the cached entry,
 1468 so that the iteration strategy can mark the cache entry as stable.
 1469

1470 We will first evaluate our existing implementation before optimizing our fixpoint stack
 1471 using various caching strategies. To do this, we implement a constant-propagation analysis
 1472 for `WebAssembly`.
 1473

1474 7.3 Evaluation of Scala Fixpoint Combinators on WebAssembly Analyses

1475 To demonstrate the practical significance of the Scala fixpoint combinators, we evaluate their
 1476 performance on two existing and one new interval analyses for `WebAssembly 1.0` (`Wasm`).
 1477 The two existing `Wasm` analyses stem from our prior work [5], where we detail the abstract
 1478
 1479

domain and evaluate the precision of the analyses. However, a performance evaluation was missing. In this subsection, we close this gap in and compare the performance of different iteration strategies for the three Wasm analysis on programs from the benchmarks game.

Analysis Setup. We run three Wasm analyses: a type analysis, a constant analysis, and an interval analysis. Wasm features four primitive value types: integers and floating-point numbers with 32 and 64 bits. The analyses differ in how they abstract these primitive types:

```

enum AbsValue[I32, I64, F32, F64]:
  case I32Val(i: I32)
  case I64Val(i: I64)
  case F32Val(f: F32)
  case F64Val(f: F64)
  case Top
type TValue = AbsValue[I32Type, I64Type, F32Type, F64Type]
type ConstValue = AbsValue[Const[Int], Const[Long], Const[Float], Const[Double]]
type IntervalValue = AbsValue[IV[Int], IV[Long], Const[Float], Const[Double]]
enum Const[A]:
  case Actual(a: A)
  case Top
enum IV[B]:
  case Bounded(lower: B, upper: B)
  case Top

```

The interval analysis is novel, whereas the type and constant analyses were described in prior work [5]. A key challenge for Wasm analyses is that functions and memory can be accessed through 32-bit integers. Therefore, our interval analysis features function and memory access through interval ranges. On the other hand, our interval analysis has only rudimentary support for floating point numbers via constants, as a sound interval approximation would require modeling the complex rounding semantics of floating-point operations.

Wasm contains two sources of looping: recursive function calls and loop instructions. The analyses use fixpoint combinators to focus on these constructs, the iteration strategies from Section 7.1, and the fixpoint stack from Section 7.2. Besides showing the practical usability of our fixpoint approach, we also want to compare the impact of the iteration strategies on the analysis performance. To this end, we left the iteration strategy configurable in the analysis definition and evaluate each analysis with each iteration strategy: innermost, outermost, and topmost.

We ran the analyses on 8 programs from the benchmarks game,¹⁰ which were implemented in C and compiled to Wasm with the emscripten compiler.¹¹ The compiled programs have between 331 and 8412 lines of Wasm code (Figure 4). For each analyzed program, we ran the analysis 10 times after a JVM warmup and averaged the running times. We ran the experiments on an 8-core M2 MacBook Air with 24 GB of RAM.

Results. We show the average running times (with confidence intervals) of each of analysis and each iteration strategy on each of the 8 programs in Figure 4. First, we can observe that the analysis running times grow with the precision of the abstract domain, as was to be expected. Second, while $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ and $\phi_{\text{outermost}}$ are on par, combinator ϕ_{topmost} performs

¹⁰<https://benchmarksgame-team.pages.debian.net/benchmarksgame/index.html>

¹¹<https://emscripten.org/>

Fig. 4. (Top) Size of the benchmarked WebAssembly programs, measured by `cloc`. (Bottom) Running times of different iteration strategies for a type, constant, and interval analyses for WebAssembly on programs of the benchmarks game. The plots report average execution times on a logarithmic scale (lower values indicate better performance).

much worse in many cases. The reason is that ϕ_{topmost} redundantly reanalyzes many SCGs during each iteration, even though their result remains the same. Third, the overall running times of $\phi_{\text{innermost}}$ and $\phi_{\text{outermost}}$ are reasonably fast and permit practical application of the analysis. However, programs `binarytrees` and `k-nucleotide` already require noticeable analysis

time with the interval analysis, which may indicate a scalability issue. In [Section 8](#), we show how we can improve the analysis performance for these cases by more than a 10X speedup.

In summary, our Wasm experiment demonstrates the following points:

- Our fixpoint combinators are independent of the meta-language: We have used them in Haskell and Scala.
- Our fixpoint combinators are independent of the object-language: We have used them to analyze Stratego, Scheme, and Wasm.
- Our fixpoint combinators are independent of the abstract domain: We have used them for sort analysis (Stratego), CFA (Scheme), type, constant, and interval analysis (Wasm).

8 Improving Cache Usage in the Fixpoint Stack

We introduce two improvements of `FixStack` that increase the analysis performance through better cache utilization.

8.1 Reusing Non-Recursive Results

By default, `FixStack` caches only the results of recursive calls of the abstract interpreter. Specifically, when a co-recurrent call is popped, we store its result in the cache. If the result was stable, we use it to skip subsequent calls that use the same analysis state (Line 18 in [Figure 3](#)).

We can use the same mechanism to cache and reuse non-recursive analysis results if they are stable. This requires only one change: In `pop`, when a call is not corecurrent, use a variant of `storeCorecurrentOutput` to store its output in the cache nonetheless. However, for non-recursive calls, we use a join instead of widening to retain precision. The relevant code in `pop` becomes:

```
def pop(in: In, out: Out): PopResult =
  inWidening.pop(in) // pop call from stack
  stack.remove(in)
  val isCorecurrent = corecurrentCalls.remove(stack.size)
  if (isCorecurrent) storeOutput(in, out, widen=true)
  else storeOutput(in, out, widen=false) match
    case PopResult.Stable(entry) => PopResult.Stable(entry)
    case PopResult.Unstable(out) => PopResult.Stable(outCache(in))
```

Notably, a non-recursive call still yields a `Stable` result as before, even when the cached entry grows. This is because non-recursive calls do not require iteration. When the iteration strategy marks the returned cache entry as stable, we can reuse the non-recursive result in subsequent invocations of `push`. We evaluate the impact of this improvement at the end of the section.

8.2 Reusing Intermediate Results

By default, `FixStack` reuses only cache entries for stable results, for which we have found a fixpoint already. However, in highly recursive code, this means we reanalyze interpreter calls many times, because only root SCG entries are marked stable. For example, consider if we analyze the following program with mutually recursive functions `f` and `g`: No matter which iteration strategy we choose, we only obtain cache entries for `f`, because it is the head of the outermost SCG. In particular, `g` is also recursive, but its analysis result cannot

```

1633 main = f 10
1634 f x = if (random) 1 else g x + g (x+1) + g (x+2)
1635 g x = if (x == 1) 1 else f x + g (x-1)

```

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be marked stable until `f` is stable. Therefore, we reanalyze `g` many times in each iteration even though the analysis result of `g` only changes when we learn something new about `f`. We can improve the caching behavior of our abstract interpreter by reusing intermediate *unstable* results. We can reuse unstable results from the cache as long as we ensure to update them at least once during each fixpoint iteration, as not to jeopardize termination. While, in principal, this can lead to slower fixpoint computations, we found that it improves the analysis performance significantly. For innermost, an unoptimized interval analysis invokes 299 recursive yet non-recurrent calls for the given example, whereas reusing the intermediate results only invokes 77 recursive calls, because 57 recursive calls can reuse intermediate results and therefore are skipped. The other iteration strategies, we see similar improvements.

To reuse intermediate results, we first modify the check in `push` that determines whether a cache entry may be reused. In particular, we relax the requirement that a cache entry must be stable (Line 16 of Figure 3), and also allow the reuse of unstable entries. However, to ensure that cache entries are updated often enough, we introduce a third stability alternative `Stability.Outdated`. At the beginning of each iteration, the relevant previous cache entries must be marked `Outdated` if they are `Unstable`. But rather than scanning the entire cache and invalidating all unstable cache entries, we instead add dependency tracking between cache entries.

To track dependencies, we add a field `CacheEntry.dependencies: Set[CacheEntry]` to store links to the cache entries of directly recursive interpreter calls that originate from the current call. We track these cache entries by introducing a `dependencyStack: List[List[CacheEntry]]` to `FixStack`. In `FixStack.push`, we push an empty dependency list on top of `dependencyStack`. And in `FixStack.pop`, we pop the `dependencyStack` and register these dependencies with the current cache entry, and then we also add the current cache entry to the parent's dependency list. This way, each cache entry links to its direct dependencies. At beginning of each fixpoint iteration, we find the previous cache entry and transitively invalidate all unstable cache entries that the entry depends on.

8.3 Evaluating the Improved Fixpoint Stack

In this subsection, we evaluate the performance optimizations for the fixpoint algorithms of `WebAssembly` and `Datalog` analyses.

8.3.1 Speedup for WebAssembly Analyses

We first evaluate the speedup of the performance optimizations on the type, constant, and interval analyses for `WebAssembly` on 8 programs from the benchmarks game. The experiment setup is the same as in Section 7.3.

Results. Figure 5 reports on the average speedup. On average, the speedup is greater for the interval analyses, because more performance can be gained with improved iteration strategies that ascend the infinitely high interval lattice faster. Furthermore, the speedup is greater for larger programs like `k-nucleotide` (8412 loc) and `binarytrees` (3293 loc), because these

Fig. 5. Absolute execution time (top) and speedup (bottom) of performance optimizations for different iteration strategies for three WebAssembly analyses on programs of the benchmarks game.

Fig. 6. Running times of different iteration and caching strategies for a constant analysis for two Datalog programs. The plots report execution time in milliseconds on a logarithmic scale (lower values indicate better performance). TO indicates a timeout (> 30 min runtime).

programs have more SCGs and benefit from improved iteration strategies. Only in a few cases there is a minor slow down in the range of milliseconds. This lets us conclude that the optimizations are net benefit for the WebAssembly analyses.

In summary, this case study makes the following point:

- WebAssembly analyses benefit from our optimizations described in this section. The speedup is larger for analyses with taller lattices and for larger programs.

8.3.2 Speedup for Datalog

We implemented a constant-propagation analysis for Datalog to benchmark the performance characteristics of our reengineered fixpoint stack, including the new caching strategies. To this end, we integrated our Scala-based Sturdy framework into the IncA compiler framework for Datalog [24]. IncA enables us to analyze Datalog programs originating from a variety of frontend languages. Datalog presents a particularly interesting target for evaluating our fixpoint algorithm, due to its extensive use of recursion.

Analysis Setup. Our abstract interpreter takes a Datalog program consisting of a set of rules and predefined facts as input. During evaluation, it updates a supplementary table for variable

bindings and tracks a set of errors. We abstract values with a finite constant abstract domain, i.e., abstract values are either strings, integers, algebraic data, or \top . We abstract relations by tracking one abstract value per column.

```

1786 enum ConstantValue:
1787     case Top
1788     case ConstantString(s: String)
1789     case ConstantInt(i: Int)
1790     case ConstantADT(ctr: String, args: Seq[ConstantValue])
1791
1792 type ConstantRelation = Map[String, ConstantValue]
1793
1794
1795
1796

```

We analyze two input programs: (i) a large-scale, handwritten, self-contained DOOP analysis [6] implemented in the Soufflé dialect of Datalog [41]¹² (143 rules), and (ii) a Datalog program generated from a purely functional source language¹³ (107 rules), using the functional IncA compiler [31].

To measure analysis performance, we conducted five measurements after JVM warmup. From these, we averaged the three fastest executions to remove potential outliers. All experiments were carried out on an 8-core M2 MacBook Air with 24 GB of RAM.

Results. Figure 6 shows analysis times for innermost, outermost and topmost iteration strategies with different caching methods on both Datalog programs. Innermost consistently performs best, while topmost is always the slowest strategy. This aligns with expectations, as Datalog programs often contain many small SCGs that do not align well with the caching behavior of the topmost strategy.

Reusing stable (non-)recursive results improves performance across all strategies for both programs by a factor of $\sim 1.1\times$ to $\sim 1.6\times$. However, storing *intermediate recursive results* has a far greater impact for recursive Datalog. For the DOOP program, this yields a 3-fold to 43-fold performance improvement. For the functional IncA program, it is essential; without it, all strategies time out (TO), requiring at least 30 minutes. Caching intermediate recursive results reduces this to under 30 seconds for all strategies.

The performance differences between analyzing the DOOP and functional IncA programs arise from structural differences caused by the compilation approach used in functional IncA. Specifically, the functional IncA compiler applies a Datalog-specific transformation called demand transformation [48]. This transformation has two major side effects: (i) it duplicates code in the resulting Datalog program, and (ii) it introduces new recursive rules. Consequently, the functional IncA program contains the same recursive calls multiple times and therefore benefits more from caching them.

The benefits of caching are especially pronounced when combining caching of intermediate recursive and non-recursive results. Without caching both, the functional IncA program is orders of magnitude slower to analyze than DOOP. However, with full caching, its analysis speed matches that of the DOOP program. Ultimately, for both benchmarks, combining the two caching strategies reduces analysis time to under 400ms, regardless of the iteration strategy used.

¹²<https://gitlab.rlp.net/plmz/inca-scala/-/blob/abstract-interpretation/inca-casestudy/src/main/resources/doop/micro.dl>

¹³<https://gitlab.rlp.net/plmz/inca-scala/-/blob/abstract-interpretation/inca-fun/src/test/resources/functional/controlflow/CFlow.fina>

1837 This case study illustrates two key insights:

- 1838 • Efficient caching within the fixpoint algorithm is essential for analysis of recursion-
1839 intensive languages such as Datalog.
- 1840 • The choice of iteration strategy is less important if we use efficient caching strategies.

1842 9 Related Work

1843 The focus of this work is the modular description of fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract
1844 interpreters. In this section, we discuss work related to our approach presented in this paper.

1845 *Modularizing the Definition and Soundness Proofs of Big-Step Abstract Interpreters.* There
1846 have been several works that modularized different parts of the definition and soundness proofs
1847 of big-step abstract interpreters. Keidel et al. [22] describe an approach that modularizes
1848 the concrete and abstract language semantics and its soundness proof with *arrows* [15]. In
1849 particular, the concrete and abstract semantics is derived from the same *generic interpreter*
1850 that is composed of a number of primitive operations over values, stores, exceptions, etc. The
1851 benefit of this approach is that it guarantees that an entire analysis is sound, as long as each
1852 operation is sound. However, Keidel et al. [22] do not show a fixpoint algorithm nor do they
1853 describe how a fixpoint algorithm should be implemented.

1854 Bodin et al. [3] describe a similar approach that derives both the concrete and abstract
1855 semantics from the same *skeletal semantics*. However, compared to arrows used by Keidel
1856 et al. [22], they use a more liberal algebra called *skeletons*, which consists of hooks, filters,
1857 and branching operations. Yet, they provide similar soundness guarantees: an entire analysis
1858 derived from a skeletal semantics is sound, as long as all of its operations are sound. Bodin
1859 et al. [3, Section 5.4] define the abstract semantics as the greatest fixpoint of the abstract
1860 collecting semantics. However, they do not show an algorithm that computes this fixpoint,
1861 nor do they explain how such an algorithm can be described modularly.

1862 Keidel and Erdweg [18] describe an approach that modularizes the *effects* of the analyzed
1863 language, such as exceptions and store mutations. More specifically, the approach captures the
1864 analysis of each effect with an *analysis component* which consists of a concrete and abstract
1865 *arrow transformer*. This approach simplifies the analysis of languages with multiple effects
1866 that interact with each other. Keidel and Erdweg define a single analysis for the fixpoint
1867 algorithm. However, they do not describe the fixpoint algorithm itself, nor do they describe
1868 how it can be decomposed further. In the present work, we make use of arrows and arrow
1869 transformers to modularize the description of fixpoint algorithms by the means of sound
1870 and reusable fixpoint combinators. We use arrows to describe fixpoint combinators that are
1871 independent of the type of the fixpoint computation. This allows us to change the type of the
1872 fixpoint computation, without needing to change the definition of the fixpoint combinators.

1873 Darais et al. [9] describe an approach that derives several *collecting semantics* from the
1874 same generic semantics with different combinators. These combinators, for example, collect a
1875 trace of the abstract interpreter, they collect expressions that are dead code, or they compute a
1876 fixpoint. These combinators inspired the style of fixpoint combinators we present in this paper,
1877 in that our fixpoint combinators have the same type as Darais et al. combinators. However,
1878 Darais et al. do not describe a formal theory for these combinators which makes it hard to
1879 reason about their soundness. In this work, we developed a framework for modular fixpoint
1880 algorithms that is based on fixpoint combinators. This framework allows us to describe a
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1888 family of fixpoint algorithms that can be configured and fine-tuned more easily, as we show
 1889 in our evaluation. Furthermore, we developed a formal theory about these algorithms which
 1890 allows us to prove their soundness compositionally.

1891
 1892 *Fixpoint Algorithms for Big-Step Abstract Interpreters.* The space of fixpoint algorithms
 1893 for big-step abstract interpreters has not been extensively studied yet. Schmidt [38, 40]
 1894 describes one of the first fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract interpreters that operates
 1895 on the derivation tree. The fixpoint algorithm unfolds the abstract derivation tree until each
 1896 branch either terminates or repeats itself. The algorithm detects recurrent calls of the abstract
 1897 interpreter by memoizing parts of the abstract derivation tree. If the algorithm finds a recurrent
 1898 node in a branch, it cuts off recursion to avoid non-termination which satisfies *Condition*
 1899 *1*. Furthermore, the fixpoint algorithm satisfies *Condition 2* by joining the environments
 1900 of repeating expressions with a widening operator that ensures that infinite recursive call
 1901 chains have a recurrent call. However, many details about how this algorithm actual could be
 1902 implemented are missing. Specifically, Schmidt does not explain how SCGs are calculated and
 1903 on which calls the algorithm iterates. Instead, the algorithm generates a number of recursive
 1904 equations, which then can be solved with an arbitrary iteration order to calculate the fixpoint.
 1905 We combine Schmidt’s solutions to the termination conditions to implement our initial
 1906 fixpoint algorithm `fixmonolithic` in [Section 2](#), which we later modularize. However, instead
 1907 of generating recursive equations, our algorithm `fixmonolithic` specifies an iteration order,
 1908 i.e., the algorithm iterates on the innermost SCGs of the trace of the abstract interpreter [4].

1909
 1910 Darais et al. [9] present another fixpoint algorithm for big-step abstract interpreters, similar
 1911 to *parallel fixpoint iteration*. We implemented this algorithm in [Section 4](#) with the combinator
 1912 φ_{topmost} . The algorithm uses two caches to remember the analysis result of two consecutive
 1913 fixpoint iterations. The algorithm then iterates over the entire program, updating the cache of
 1914 the most recent iteration. If none of the caches change anymore, the algorithm has reached
 1915 a fixpoint and terminates. The algorithm satisfies *Condition 1* by detecting recurrent calls
 1916 if they have an existing cache entry. However, the algorithm does not satisfy the other two
 1917 conditions which means that it does not terminate for infinite abstract domains.

1918
 1919 Wei et al. [51] introduce a technique to transform an analysis in form of an abstract machine
 1920 [14] into a big-step abstract interpreter. The resulting big-step abstract interpreter computes a
 1921 fixpoint using Darais et al.’s [2017] algorithm [51, section 6.2.3].

1922
 1923
 1924 *Minimal Function Graphs.* Fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract interpreters are related to
 1925 computing the minimal function graphs [16, 17, 36]. A *minimal function graph* of a function
 1926 call $f(x_1)$ is a set of tuples $\{(x_1, f(x_1)) \dots (x_n, f(x_n))\}$ of arguments to results of f . The set
 1927 of arguments includes the top-most argument x_1 and all recursively called arguments $x_2 \dots x_n$.
 1928 The graph is *minimal* because it does not include arguments which are never called during
 1929 the evaluation of $f(x_1)$. A fixpoint algorithm that computes the minimal abstract function
 1930 graph starts with the initial graph $\{(x_1, \perp)\}$ and then analyzes the program. On recursive calls
 1931 the algorithm looks up the argument in the graph and returns its current result, or if absent
 1932 initializes the result with \perp . The algorithm keeps track of dependencies between recursive
 1933 calls with, e.g., a worklist and iterates until the minimal function graph does not change
 1934 anymore and the worklist is empty.

1935
 1936 We view our big-step fixpoint algorithms as an extension of algorithms that compute the
 1937 minimal function graph. Specifically, the cache in [Listing 2](#) tracks the minimal function graph

1939 and the stack and SCG track the dependencies between calls. In addition, our work describes
1940 a modular implementation of fixpoint algorithms by the means of fixpoint combinators.

1941
1942 *Chaotic Fixpoint Iteration.* We focus on chaotic fixpoint iteration because it is the most
1943 popular algorithm to solve a set of recursive equations in abstract interpretation [2, 4, 13, 23].
1944 Chaotic iteration strategies iterate on small parts of the analyzed program and hence are
1945 typically more efficient than parallel iteration strategies [9], which iterate on the entire
1946 analyzed program. On the downside, chaotic iteration strategies are more complicated to
1947 implement, because they need to keep track of SCGs. However, we were able to encapsulate
1948 this complexity within reusable combinators, which are easier to use.

1949 Bourdoncle [4] presents a chaotic iteration order that is based on a weak topological
1950 ordering of the control-flow graph. The iteration order is computed before running the analysis,
1951 which requires knowing the control-flow graph ahead of time. The iteration order improves
1952 the precision as it reduces the number of widening points to the heads of SCGs. Bourdoncle
1953 [4]’s work inspired the design of the fixpoint combinators $\varphi_{\text{innermost}}$ and $\varphi_{\text{outermost}}$ that we
1954 developed in this paper, as they use the same widening points. However, in contrast, our
1955 fixpoint combinators compute the iteration order dynamically while the analysis is running.
1956 This means our fixpoint algorithms do not need to know the control-flow graph ahead of time
1957 and can dynamically fine-tune and adapt the iteration order if needed.

1958
1959
1960 *Fixpoint Algorithms for Small-Step Abstract Interpreters.* In contrast to big-step abstract
1961 interpreters, static analyses in small-step style have a longer history of research [14, 29, 42, 43].
1962 Similar to big-step abstract interpreters, small-step abstract interpreters also seamlessly
1963 combine data-flow and control-flow information. However, they describe the abstract semantics
1964 as a small-step relation. A fixpoint algorithm for such interpreters explores the finite state space
1965 of the small-step relation. Unfortunately, it is unclear how small-step fixpoint algorithms
1966 apply to big-step abstract interpreters, because of differences in the style of semantics:
1967 While small-step abstract interpreters use continuations to explicitly model control of the
1968 interpreter as part of the state space, big-step abstract interpreters leverage the control of the
1969 meta-language (e.g., Haskell). This means that big-step abstract interpreters cannot ensure
1970 termination simply by making the state space finite, because their interpreter function may
1971 diverge nonetheless. To this end, big-step fixpoint algorithms must detect recurrent recursive
1972 calls and iterate on them which is not necessary for small-step algorithms.

1973 1974 1975 1976 **10 Conclusion**

1977 In this paper, we studied the modular description of fixpoint algorithms for big-step abstract
1978 interpreters. We identified three conditions that guarantee the termination of big-step fixpoint
1979 algorithms. Based on these conditions, we developed a fixpoint algorithm for big-step abstract
1980 interpreters that iterates on the strongly-connected subgraphs of the graph-shaped trace.
1981 However, since the algorithm consists of a single monolithic function, it is hard to extend,
1982 configure and adapt the fixpoint algorithm. To this end, we refactored the algorithm into
1983 small reusable fixpoint combinators which allow us to change the algorithm by rearranging
1984 and adding new combinators. Furthermore, the combinators simplify the soundness proof, as
1985 each combinator can be proved sound individually once and for all. Moreover, our evaluation
1986 demonstrates that our approach describes an entire family of fixpoint algorithms for different
1987 languages and analyses that can be easily extended, adapted and configured. Lastly, the fixpoint
1988
1989

combinators have been reimplemented in Scala and used to develop fixpoint algorithms that scale to analyze real-world WebAssembly programs.

11 Data Availability Statement

The artifact accompanying this paper is publicly available at Zenodo and includes the Haskell code of the fixpoint combinators and the case studies [21]. The Scala implementation of Sturdy discussed in section 7 and section 8 is available at <https://gitlab.rlp.net/plmz/sturdy.scala>. The abstract interpreter for Datalog used in section 8.3 is available at <https://gitlab.rlp.net/plmz/inca-scala/-/tree/abstract-interpretation>.

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